

Technische Universität Berlin
Urban Management
Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft

Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach

Case Study: Merida City, Mexico

Fátima Xóchitl Bravo Lara

Supervised by: Dr.-Ing. Wulf-Holger Arndt
Head of the Area of Mobility and Space of the
Center for Technology and Society

Berlin, Germany, 2024

Technische Universität Berlin
Urban Management
Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft

**Enhancement of
Active Mobility through
Smart City Approach
Case Study: Merida City, Mexico**

Master's thesis at the Center for Technology and Society of the TU Berlin
in Course: Urban Management

Presented by: Fátima Xóchitl Bravo Lara

Supervised by: Dr.-Ing. Wulf-Holger Arndt, Head of Area „Mobility and Space,
“Center for Technology and Society

TABLE OF CONTENT

LIST OF FIGURES 5

LIST OF TABLES..... 5

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS 7

Statement of Authenticity 9

Abstract 11

Acknowledgments 13

1 Introduction 15

1.1 Context 15

1.2 Problem Statement 15

1.3 Objectives and Limitations 15

1.4 Research Questions 16

1.5 Scope 16

1.6 Motivation 17

1.7 Relevance and significance of the topic 17

2 Methodology 19

2.1 Data Research Method 19

2.2 Research Flow Diagram..... 19

2.3 Primary data collection and analysis 20

2.4 Secondary Data Review..... 20

3 The Smart City Approach 21

3.1 Contextualizing the Smart City concept..... 21

3.1.1 Global Urban Growth 21

3.1.2 Need for Sustainable Development..... 21

3.2 Smart City Definition 23

3.2.1 Dimensions of the Smart City 24

3.2.2 Considerations regarding the Smart City approach..... 25

3.2.3 Examples of Smart City implementation..... 27

4 Mobility within an Urban Context 29

4.1 Sustainable Transport as a component of Mobility 29

4.1.1 Definition of Transport 29

4.1.2 Sustainable Transport Context 29

4.1.3 Definition of Sustainable Transport..... 30

4.1.4 Transport Transition in Mexico 30

4.2 Definition of Mobility..... 31

4.2.1 Sustainable Mobility 31

4.2.2 Smart Mobility 32

4.2.3 Active Mobility in Urban Areas..... 35

5	Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach	39
5.1	Recap of the previous chapters.....	39
5.2	Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach.....	40
5.3	Examples of Active Mobility enhanced by Smart City approaches	41
6	Case Study: Merida City	45
6.1	National Context: Mexico	45
6.1.1	Location and Geography of Mexico	45
6.1.2	Political Division	46
6.1.3	Population of Mexico	46
6.1.4	Mexico: an emerging country.....	46
6.1.5	Legal Actions towards Sustainability in Mexico	47
6.1.6	Mobility policies and laws in Mexico	47
6.1.7	Smart City Initiatives in Mexico	48
6.2	Regional Context in Mexico: South-East Region.....	50
6.2.1	Regional Division of Mexico.....	50
6.2.2	Regional Development in Mexico	51
6.3	Local Context: Yucatan State and Merida City	52
6.3.1	Geographic Context.....	52
6.3.2	Sociodemographic Context of Merida	53
6.3.3	Mobility in Merida.....	53
6.3.4	Active Mobility in Merida	56
6.3.5	Smart City Approaches in Merida	60
7	Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach in Merida	63
7.1	Existing enhancement of Active Mobility with Smart City approach in Merida ..	64
7.1.1	Indirect enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City approach.....	64
7.1.2	Direct enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City approach	65
7.2	Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Merida: promotion of walking and cycling	66
7.2.1	Areas of opportunity.....	67
7.2.2	Resilience and Adaptability.....	68
7.2.3	Effect of Smart City promotion of Active Modes in Merida	68
8	Analysis and Transferability	69
9	Conclusions.....	73
10	List of References	77
11	Figures and Tables Sources	89
12	Attachments.....	91

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Merida City location.....	16
Figure 2: Research flow diagram.	19
Figure 3: Sustainable Development Goals.....	22
Figure 4: Smart City fields of action (Giffinger et al. 2007)	24
Figure 5: Smart Cities Wheel	25
Figure 6: Walkability Evaluation	35
Figure 7: Mexico Map	45
Figure 8: Mexico's Political Division	46
Figure 9: Mexico Regions.....	50
Figure 10: South-east Region	50
Figure 11: Merida City location.....	52
Figure 12: Merida Geomorphology.....	52
Figure 13: Road network and urbanized area of the municipality of Merida.....	53
Figure 14: Modal Split in Merida.....	54
Figure 15: Paseo de Montejo Avenue	56
Figure 16: Comparison of cross sections of Paseo Montejo.....	57
Figure 17: Bicycle racks in public transport in Merida.....	58
Figure 18: En Bici campaign	58

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Main Passenger Modal Options	29
Table 2: Summary and comparison among concepts:.....	42
Table 3: Distribution of points in 2021 by evaluation axis of Mérida, Yucatán.....	59
Table 4: Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Merida.....	66

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BRT – Bus Rapid Transport

C5 - Command, Control, Computing, Communications and Citizen Contact Center of CDMX

C5i - Center for Control, Command, Communications, Computing, Coordination and Intelligence in Merida

Cctv - Closed-circuit television

CDMX - Abbreviation in Spanish for Ciudad de México | English: Mexico City

CEPAL – Spanish for ECLAC: Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean

CO2 – Carbon Dioxide

COP 21 – United Nations Climate Change Conference in Paris

COP 26 – United Nations Climate Change Conference in Glasgow

COP 27 – United Nations Climate Change Conference in Sharm el-Sheikh

COP 28 – United Nations Climate Change Conference in Dubai

E7 – Emerging Seven

EU – European Union

GHG – Global greenhouse gas emissions

HLAG-ST - High-Level Advisory Group on Sustainable Transport

ICT - Information and Communication Technologies

IBM - International Business Machines Corporation

IMDUT – Yucatan’s Institute of Mobility and Territorial Urban Development

INEGI – Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía | English: National Institute of Statistics and Geography

IoT - Internet of Things

ITS - Intelligent Transportation System

JPOI - Johannesburg Plan of Implementation

KRITIS – Germany’s National Strategy for the Protection of Critical Infrastructures

LGCC - Ley General de Cambio Climático | English: General Law on Climate Change

MaaS - Mobility as Service

MoD - Mobility on Demand

NDC - Nationally determined contribution

OECD - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

PPP- Public-private partnerships

RATP - La Régie Autonome des Transports Parisiens | English: The Autonomous Authority of Parisian Transport

Rio +20 - United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development

SCELC - Smart City Expo Latam Congress

SDG - Sustainable Development Goals

SET Plan - Strategic Energy Technology Plan of European Union

SNCF – Société nationale des chemins de fer français | English: National Company of French Railways

SRE – Secretaría de Relaciones Exteriores | English: Ministry of Foreign Affairs

SUMP - Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans

UN – United Nations

UNFCCC - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UN-Habitat - United Nations Human Settlements Programme

U.S. – United States of America

USTDA - United States Trade and Development Agency

ZTG - Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft | English: Center for Technology and Society

Statement of Authenticity

This thesis contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the research contains no material previously published or written by another person except where due reference has been made in the thesis text.

Fátima Xóchitl Bravo Lara

Berlin, August 31st, 2024

Abstract

Keywords: Mobility, Smart City, Smart Mobility, Active Mobility, Merida

The Twentieth Century was characterized by the rapid growth of cities throughout the globe. With the transition into the twenty-first century, urbanization efforts focus on a transition to create more efficient, inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban settlements. A vital element of these efforts is urban mobility. Within this context, two different mobility approaches have emerged as focal points under the sustainable mobility goal: Smart Mobility and Active Mobility. Smart Mobility proposes the integration of advanced technologies and data-driven solutions to create efficient and sustainable transport systems. Parallely, Active Mobility encourages non-motorized transport, such as walking and cycling, as alternative modes of transportation, incorporating physical activity and healthier lifestyles while reducing environmental impacts.

Through a transdisciplinary approach that includes urban planning, urban design, transportation, sustainability, technology, and governance, this research explores how Smart Mobility approaches could enhance Active Mobility in a city in an emerging country, such as Merida City in Mexico. As a case study, Merida is relevant due to its rapid urban growth, the background and the implementation of Smart City approaches, and the conditions and aspiration to be a model of sustainable urban development.

This master thesis aims to provide valuable insights that extend beyond Merida City, serving as a reference throughout the globe for other cities with similar characteristics and who face similar mobility challenges.

Acknowledgments

I am deeply thankful to God for giving me the strength, constancy, and perseverance to achieve everything I have done and will do.

I want to dedicate this arduous Masterarbeit to my Mom, who not only gave me life but also provided all the tools to stand out and thrive in this world. She instilled in me values, love, and unwavering support. Through her example, I learned about responsibility, commitment, strength, and passion. Thank you, dear Ana María, for giving me the wings to fly as high and far as I want to. Thanks to my Dad, Alberto, who taught me to live each day as if it were the last. Thank you for being next to me throughout all the way, guiding, protecting, and loving me despite the time and space rules. I love you both with all my heart.

Thanks to my home country, Mexico, for giving me an excellent formation that allowed me to develop adequately in any setting throughout the globe. Thanks especially to “El Fondo para el Desarrollo de Recursos Humanos (FIDERH)” for believing in my potential and supporting it.

Thanks to my (second) home country, Germany, for opening the doors to me and allowing me to learn from its warm-hearted and intellectually stimulating people. I want to thank especially the Friedrich Naumann Stiftung (FNS) for giving me the opportunity and honor to become the first Mexican student to be awarded a scholarship from this Institution. I am deeply grateful.

I would also like to thank the Technische Universität Berlin and the Urban Management Program, especially its coordinator, Dr. Bettina Hamann, for all the professional and personal teachings and lessons.

Mainly, I want to express my gratitude to my supervisor, Dr.-Ing. Wulf-Holger Arndt, for his support and guidance provided throughout the development of this project. His suggestions and feedback helped me shape this work, contributing significantly to its structural integrity, cohesiveness, and overall excellence.

Gratitude to the experts at the Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft, Technische Universität Berlin and Colegio Yucateco de Arquitectos for their valuable insights.

Last but not least, I feel grateful to have gone through this experience accompanied by friends and colleagues who made this journey more enjoyable. Thank you for providing different perspectives and insights.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The global market's expansion in the twentieth century led to the creation of the concept of emerging markets, which derived into the term emerging countries. The country of Mexico has been part of this trend and, since the twentieth century, has started to open its economy to the global arena, propelling its transition into an emerging country (Blázquez and Santiso, 2003). As this transformation took place, the country's urban landscape has gone through significant changes, especially in urban areas, where approximately 81% of the Mexican population resided in 2022 (Grupo Banco Mundial, 2023).

The Mexican urbanization trend mirrors a global phenomenon predicted by the United Nations Human Settlements Programme UN-Habitat (Khor, 2022, p. 3): by 2050, approximately 68% of the world's population will be living in urban areas. In response to this rapid urbanization, Mexican cities have devised diverse strategies to address the challenges related to urban growth, including urban mobility.

Parallel to this, the Smart City concept emerged in the late twentieth century and early twenty-first (University of Alberta, 2017). In Mexico, during this twenty-first century, different states have adopted Smart City approaches, for example, Mexico City, Puebla, Querétaro, and Jalisco (Guarneros Olmos, 2023). In 2015, Merida City started implementing digital tools that started the city's technological transformation, especially regarding Smart Mobility (Fernández, 2015).

The twenty-first century has been characterized by a global pursuit of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban settlements (United Nations Department for Economic and Social Affairs, 2023, p. 34). Active Mobility has become a prominent trend in this context because it encourages physical activity, a healthier lifestyle, and environmentally friendly transportation options (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p. 1,2).

1.2 Problem Statement

Nowadays, as part of a decentralization project and significant investments in the region (López Obrador, 2017), combined with its reputation for safety, Merida is rapidly emerging as an attractive destination for investors and residents alike (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2021b). This influx of people has developed pressure on housing availability, services, infrastructure, and environmental consequences.

In this evolving landscape, integrating Smart Mobility approaches into Merida's urban transport system emerges as a critical inquiry. This thesis explores how such approaches can be effectively harnessed to promote and enhance Active Mobility options, contributing to Merida's sustainable urban development and offering insights for other emerging cities worldwide facing similar challenges.

1.3 Objectives and Limitations

The main goal of this research project is to establish how Smart Mobility approaches can be integrated into the urban transport system to promote and enhance Active Mobility in a middle-sized city in an emerging country. Merida City will be used as a case study.

In order to establish this integration, several goals are determined. Among them is the research on Smart Mobility and Active Mobility. It is also relevant to establish the current state of urban mobility in Merida City, with the existing infrastructure and transportation modes. Then, it is necessary to set up the potential applications of Smart Mobility within the Merida City context. After these potential applications have been set up, the next step is to demonstrate the relationship between Smart Mobility and Active Mobility (including walking and cycling). At this point, the challenges and barriers related to the implementation of smart and Active Mobility initiatives will be identified. Finally, strategies and recommendations will

be established, and evidence of how this integration could be replicated in other cities around the globe will be put in.

Regarding the limitations, this research will not extend to the implementation phase of the proposed Smart Mobility solutions. However, it will instead provide recommendations and strategies based on research findings. Furthermore, the research will draw from international examples, but the primary case study will remain in Merida City.

1.4 Research Questions

General research question

How can Smart Mobility approaches be integrated into the urban transport system to promote and enhance Active Mobility options in a city of an emerging country such as Mexico, in the case of Merida?

Secondary research questions

- What is Smart Mobility as an element of a Smart City?
- How can Smart City technologies improve cycling infrastructure and safety in Merida?
- What Smart City technologies can be used to improve pedestrian infrastructure and encourage walking as a mode of transport in Merida?

To answer these questions, this research adopts a mixed-method approach, with quantitative research based on statistical analysis and qualitative research focused on interviews with experts and analysis of different case studies.

1.5 Scope

The scale of the research project will be urban, but understanding it within a regional, national, and international context. Its primary geographic scope will be Merida City, located in the Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico (see Figure 1). Regarding the temporal framework, it will be mainly focused on the late twentieth and early twenty-first century. This temporal boundary provides insights for analysing the smart and Active Mobility phenomena and Merida City's recent initiatives and their actual relevance.

Figure 1: Merida City location.

Source: *Elaborated by author, 2023.*

1.6 Motivation

Living in Mexico City, the biggest Metropolis in North America and the second biggest in Latin America (Agencia Digital de Innovación Pública, 2018), has allowed me to witness the challenges that rapid and disorganized urban growth can bring, especially when it comes to mobility and infrastructure, moreover, how these impact the life quality of citizens.

In 2020, my move to Merida City showed me a contrasting dynamic within a city facing rapid growth due to a national decentralization project (López Obrador, 2017). Its privileged location, security rate, and tourist attractions are positioning Merida as an interest point for investors. Merida is emerging as a regional hub with great importance at the local, regional, national, and international levels (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2021b), which brings both opportunities and challenges. Among these are the accumulation of economic resources, protection of the environment, and provision of housing and infrastructure for the population influx. The mentioned elements set the conditions to explore how Merida (and any other city with similar characteristics) can learn from past mistakes and new learnings of larger cities like Mexico City.

Since mobility is one of the critical elements related to health, economic growth, social equity, and life quality (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p.1,2), this thesis seems necessary to shed light on the challenges related to smart and Active Mobility, and how Merida City could take advantage of them. The insights obtained in Merida's context can be applied to similar urban contexts globally.

1.7 Relevance and significance of the topic

The importance of this research topic is based on its potential to address challenges that emerging cities, such as Merida in Mexico, are facing. The current research status on smart and Active Mobility is predominantly focused on large metropolitan areas, leaving a gap in the literature concerning medium-sized cities. Also, as a relatively new area of study, integrating Smart Mobility approaches to enhance Active Mobility has received limited research in the local context. Therefore, this research fills a gap in the literature by exploring innovative strategies.

In response to their rapid urbanization, emerging cities need to enhance transportation systems that promote Active Mobility. By including walking and cycling, physical activity is increased, which can lead to a healthier lifestyle while reducing the environmental impacts (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p.1,2). Integrating Smart Mobility approaches into Merida's urban transport system can be a sustainable and efficient urban transportation solution.

This thesis can have a broader impact beyond Merida. It can be a reference for other emerging cities facing similar mobility challenges worldwide, promoting more sustainable and people-centric urbanization. This makes the research locally and globally significant.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Research Method

The research aims for a transdisciplinary approach based on the intersection between urban planning, urban design, transport, sustainability, technology, and governance. The research design uses a mixed-method approach incorporating primary and secondary data collection and analysis. The general framework for this research is mainly grounded in a theory-led thesis proposal. Due to practical considerations and time constraints, secondary data collection will prevail in this research. Nevertheless, expert interviews will be conducted as a primary source and a complementary method to enrich the subject matter and provide valuable insights into the development of this thesis.

2.2 Research Flow Diagram

Figure 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the research structure and its different phases. The research flow diagram shows the progression of the study, encompassing both secondary data, primary data collection and analysis. This diagram shows the mixed-methodological approach adopted for this thesis, highlighting the integration of diverse data sources to answer the research question comprehensively.

Figure 2: Research flow diagram.

Research Flow Diagram

Source: Elaborated by author, 2023.

2.3 Primary data collection and analysis

As mentioned in the previous section, given the time constraints, the primary data collection approach will be focused on expert interviews. The objective is to gather valuable insights and perspectives from experts with deep knowledge of the research topic. These include Experts at Center for Technology and Society, Technische Universität Berlin and Yucatan College of Architects.

For the data collection procedure, it is considered to conduct the interviews both in person and digital, using virtual communication tools, such as Zoom. These tools allow us to interact with the experts while adhering to the current geographic and time limitations.

In order to integrate the data, the main ideas, concepts, and insights gathered from the expert interviews will be integrated into the broader framework of this study. This process will provide valuable qualitative data that will complement the secondary data sources.

2.4 Secondary Data Review

The secondary data review gathers a multidimensional approach that involves diverse methods and sources to portray the research landscape. This section presents the specific methodologies that will be performed in the secondary data review.

Policy analysis

The policy analysis is a fundamental part of the secondary data review and will serve a dual objective within the research framework. The first is to portray the current mobility landscape within the local context in Merida City. This task includes the analysis of relevant policies, including the "Sectoral Infrastructure Program for Sustainable Development 2015," which marks the initial foray into digitalization efforts, and the "Integral Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan 2040," which articulates long-term mobility goals extending to the year 2040. The second objective is to compare policies regarding smart cities and Active Mobility in other countries, providing valuable insights into the global implementation of these approaches.

Campaigns Analysis

The campaign analysis plays a central role in defining the contemporary status of smart cities within the local context. Through the analysis of ongoing campaigns, this method will delineate the key elements that characterize the Smart City initiatives in Merida City.

Discourse Analysis

Discourse Analysis provides insight into the political realm, highlighting the approaches taken at the government level to understand and address development perspectives at a national and regional level.

Media Review

Media review will be based on the examination of local newspapers and magazines. This method will provide valuable insight and a holistic portrayal of the current status of the Smart City and Active Mobility initiatives within Merida City.

Literature Review

The literature review will be divided into two sections to map the actual state of the research landscape. The first section is based on the theory, exploring the concepts of Smart Mobility, Active Mobility, and their potential connection. The second section focuses on context, exploring Merida City's urban development trajectory and current mobility status. These perspectives provide a holistic foundation to understand and analyze how Smart Mobility approaches can enhance Active Mobility in the emerging urban context of Merida.

These methodological approaches ensure a multi-dimensional analysis of the research topic, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of intelligent and Active Mobility within the Merida City context and the global environment.

3 The Smart City Approach

3.1 Contextualizing the Smart City concept

3.1.1 Global Urban Growth

In 2008, the global urban population outnumbered the rural population for the first time. This milestone marked the “new urban millennium” (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023a). According to UN-Habitat (Khor, 2022, p. 3), approximately 68% of the world’s population will live in urban areas by 2050. Urban areas are estimated to produce 70 percent of the world’s gross domestic product, which derives in economic growth (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023a). Industrial capitalist cities have worked to adapt and evolve through their rapid expansion (Schipper, Emanuel and Oldenziel, 2020, p. 303). Emerging countries and their cities, such as Mexico, mirror this growth tendency. According to the World Bank (Grupo Banco Mundial, 2023), 81% of the Mexican population resided in urban areas in 2022. This urban growth worldwide has led to new trends characterized by a global pursuit of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban settlements (United Nations Department for Economic and Social Affairs, 2023, p.34).

3.1.2 Need for Sustainable Development

At the Río +20 Conference in 2012, the document “The Future We Want” was elaborated. This document contained measures for implementing sustainable development and was the prelude to the creation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (CEPAL, 2014).

United Nations (2023) defined Sustainable development as:

“[...] development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [...] For sustainable development to be achieved, it is crucial to harmonize three core elements: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection. These elements are interconnected, and all are crucial for the well-being of individuals and societies.”

In 2015, world leaders adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (See Figure 3). The SDGs are universal and applicable to all countries (United Nations, 2023a).

In an urban-focused context, the Habitat III Conference¹ took place. As a result, the New Urban Agenda was elaborated and adopted in 2016. This action-oriented document aims to mobilize Member States and key stakeholders to drive sustainable urban development at the local level. The implementation of the New Urban Agenda contributes to “... *the localization of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in an integrated manner, and to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals and targets, including Goal 11 of making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable*” (UN-Habitat, 2020b).

¹ The United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development (Habitat III) took place in Quito, Ecuador, on 20 October 2016 (UN-Habitat, 2020b).

Figure 3: Sustainable Development Goals

Source: United Nations, 2023.

Also 2015, world leaders gathered at the UN Climate Change Conference (COP21) in Paris. This event had the objective to tackle climate change and its negative impacts. The COP21 discussion led to the creation of the Paris Agreement, a legally binding international treaty. The Agreement contains long-term goals for nations to reduce global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to hold temperature increase² and reduce the risks and impacts of climate change. The Agreement also implies a periodical assessment of collective progress towards the mentioned goals and considers financial funding to developing countries. The financing considers resilience strengthening, climate change mitigation, and adaptation to climate impacts (United Nations Climate Action, 2023b). Since then, 195 parties, including Mexico, have joined the Paris Agreement (United Nations Climate Change, 2023).

² The goal is to hold global temperature increase to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels (United Nations Climate Change, 2023)

3.2 Smart City Definition

As mentioned in the previous sections, the global urban growth trend and the need for sustainable development have led to different approaches regarding urban planning and urban solutions. One of these approaches has been the Smart City one, which has gained momentum in recent years. In the last two decades, the Smart City concept has been proposed as an attempt to develop and implement ways for cities to deal with global energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and the growing population living in urban agglomerations (Abraham *et al.*, 2017 quoting Albino *et al.*, 2015).

Nevertheless, It is important to shed light on the fact that “Smart City” is a term that does not have a fixed understanding, and there are different definitions when talking about the Smart City approach (Shelton, Zook and Wiig, 2015, p. 25).

Some definitions focus on its technological approach. Since the 1950s, planners and geographers started using increasingly computational and quantitative methodologies to understand urban phenomena (Shelton, Zook and Wiig, 2015, p. 13). These approaches highlight Smart City's definition within its correlation with Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)³ as tools to deal with urban challenges (Griffor, 2017, p. 1). Under this approach, the Smart City also plays a production role as it applies these advanced ICT in order to improve and make the production and consumption of resources more efficient (Höjer and Wangel, 2015, pp. 333). A predecessor of this approach is the development of “Smart Communities” in cooperation with the State University of San Diego. Smart Communities were defined as “a geographical region whose inhabitants, organizations, and administrative institutions use information and communication technologies to transform their region to a considerable extent” (Lindskog, 2004, p. 1). Companies from the ICT sector were key players in shaping the Smart City idea at an early stage. They recognized the network of information and communication technologies as a new business for urban areas. Consequently, they started testing new solutions together with cities with the intention of contributing to overcoming urban challenges with the new technical possibilities for the intelligent network of urban infrastructure and urban services (GreenBiz Editors, 2009).

More holistic approaches understand the Smart City term in a broader sense, including improved quality of life for citizens based on their needs (Caragliu, Del Bo and Nijkamp, 2011, p. 45). Some authors, such as Hollands (2008, p. 305-310), state that most cities that identify as Smart Cities often rely on a network-like infrastructure with an economic perspective that emphasizes the role of creative and high-tech industries. This reduces the smartness with continuous learning and adaptation processes. Nevertheless, he also suggests that concepts that are also associated with smartness are citizens' access to services and social and ecological sustainability. Caragliu *et al.* (2011, p. 45) show that a Smart City can only be smart if the investment in human capital, social capital, and traditional transportation and modern ICT infrastructures promote sustainable economic growth and a high quality of life. This should go hand in hand with the sensible use of natural resources and participatory governance. Paskaleva (2011) uses three categories to describe the characteristics of smart cities. These are networked infrastructure (1), vision and strategy for creating competitive cities (2), and an approach for sustainable and inclusive cities (3). The systematic use of ICT and technologies that make efficient use of resources should aim to move into a post-fossil society, where the consumption of resources is reduced, and the quality of life of citizens, as well as the competitiveness of the local economy, is permanently increasing (Rohde and Loew, 2011, p. 19). The goal should be to improve the sustainability in the city by the promotion of the integration and networking of various urban fields of action to realize ecological and social improvements. Among these are energy, mobility, urban planning, and participatory governance (Idem., p. 5). Kourtit & Nijkamp (2012) define the key elements of a Smart City: human capital (i.e., qualified workforce), infrastructure capital (i.e., high-tech communications structures), social

³ ICT is an umbrella term which includes any communication device or application that encompasses mobile phones, computers and network software, hardware, internet, satellite systems, etc. (Griffor, 2017, p. 1).

capital (i.e., diverse and open network connections), entrepreneurial capital (e.g., creative and risk-taking business activities).

The common characteristics of a Smart City, based on 20 definitions researched by Albino et al. (2015, pp. 5-21), include the networking (of citizens, information and urban infrastructure), targeted exploitation of ICT for networking, targeted use of the resulting networks and information flows to improve ecological (especially resource conservation and climate protection), social (e.g. education, inclusion, creative potential) and economic (especially competitiveness) sustainability at city level, and utilizing the potential of an integrated perspective on urban development (Rohde and Loew, 2011, p. 9).

In summary, the Smart City approach should include ICT and social aspects (i.e., social capital and human capital) in addition to infrastructure (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 7). A Smart City should enhance sustainable economic growth, high quality of life, sensible use of natural resources, and participatory governance (Caragliu, Del Bo and Nijkamp, 2011, p. 50).

3.2.1 Dimensions of the Smart City

Giffinger *et al.* (2007, p. 10) identified six dimensions (or fields of action) for smart cities and managed them through 74 indicators (see Figure 4). The fields of dimensions go from smart economy to Smart Mobility, including smart environment, smart governance, and smart living.

Figure 4: Smart City fields of action (Giffinger et al. 2007)

Source: Elaborated by author based on Giffinger et al. (2007, p. 10), 2023

On the other hand, Boyd Cohen proposed the Smart Cities Wheel, which distinguishes among 18 fields of action (see Figure 5) (Soe, 2017).

Though both authors propose different indicators, both agree on the six dimensions of a Smart City: Smart Mobility, smart environment, smart people, smart governance, and smart living (Ibidem.).

Figure 5: Smart Cities Wheel

Source: Elaborated by author based on Boyd Cohen (2012), 2023.

3.2.2 Considerations regarding the Smart City approach

3.2.2.1 Risks in implementing Smart City technologies

In the current discussion about smart cities, critics raise concerns about the potential risks tied to excessive mechanization and the emergence of new power structures (Schweitzer, 2015, pp. 7–8). The vagueness and multidimensionality of the Smart City concept could lead to the vested interests of Smart City initiatives, as well as to the neglect of governance and participation perspective (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 26). In fact, the majority of projects are launched without adequate participation of the population in the decision-making process, in part because of the idea that smart cities should act rapidly and efficiently (Idem., 2017, p. 27). This vagueness also tends to lean towards a technology-oriented approach, where the technical feasibility is presented as an answer for urban development changes without necessarily considering the people’s needs (Laimer, 2014, pp. 4–9).

The international developments and industrial interests, as well as the political interests, shape urban development (Frost, 2015). As part of the discussion, light is shed on the fact that corporations such as IBM, Cisco, or Siemens are co-developing Smart City concepts and driving the agenda into a market-oriented setting. The uncritical transfer of private-sector competition logic to cities raises concerns about the economization of urban spaces and the possibility for companies to introduce data collection, control, and monitoring instruments, which could result in an impact on the lifestyle of citizens and their data protection (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 39).

Adding to the discussion, Hollands (2008, p. 316) highlights that it is necessary to acknowledge the importance of ICT as a component of social, economic, and cultural development. Nevertheless, it is also important to understand that technology alone cannot bring development. To do so, it is required to shift the power in ICT from business and government to communities and its inhabitants. Maintaining an equilibrium between economic growth and sustainability is vital. Therefore, the Smart City should use ITC to enhance democratic debates to know what kind of city people want to live in. According to

Halpern (Halpern, 2005, p. 508), cities and communities are networks that cooperate with the social capital norms, rules, values, and expectations of their members and the sanction actions to encompass them. Under this context, ICT can be a component of social capital that could facilitate the development of networked communities. He uses as examples the collection of collective knowledge to bring together citizens, despite their background.

On the other hand, the Association of German Cities suggests the alignment of the Smart City with sustainable urban development principles of compact, mixed-use, and use integrated urban planning model (Deutscher Städtetag, 2015, p. 6). For Abraham *et al.* (2017, pp. 39–40), Smart City concepts do not represent neither a new urban development perspective nor a new guiding principle. In fact, they should be a supplement for the existing overarching guiding principles, such as sustainability and integrated urban development. Under this integrated perspective on urban development, the Smart City strategies and ICT serve as a means to an end. Therefore, they consider that equating the terms smart and digital could be an oversimplification. In conclusion, Abraham *et al.* (ibidem.) state that in order to be smart, technologies should serve people's interests and needs, while promoting social and political participation and inclusion. Smartness should impulse fair and democratic social structures.

3.2.2.2 Resilience

Resilience is a guiding principle in risk management. On regard of infrastructure planning, resilience should lead to the introduction of reserve capacities or security surcharges (Einfeldt *et al.*, 2013). The German Federal Ministry of the Interior's "National Strategy for the Protection of Critical Infrastructures" (KRITIS) considers that some elements that need protection are transport and transportation infrastructures, energy supply, and ICT (Bundesministerium des Innern, 2009, p. 4).

Resilience could also be understood as the ability to adapt, recover, and resist crisis when it comes to spatial structures and infrastructures. Resilience could be strengthened by developing robust, learning, and resilient governance structures; as well as by maintaining or establishing adaptable, small-scale, and flexible spatial structures and infrastructures (Deutscher Städtetag, 2015, p. 10).

Smart cities could contribute or stand in the way of a city's resilience. It can contribute, for example, by applying intelligent solutions, such as intelligent power grids within built in redundancies and fast recover capabilities. However, it exists the risk as well that technology could fail in the event of a blackout. Therefore, it is vital to consider that in the current ever-growing global dependencies of urban development⁴ are increasing the unforeseeable risks for municipal services of general interest and sustainable urban development (Idem., p. 14).

3.2.2.3 Sustainability and Smartness

Currently, there is a tendency to equate a Smart City with a sustainable one. This is a consequence of the logic idea that self-controlling infrastructures and sensors can react flexibly to individual needs and save resources. However, the concepts of sustainable and smart cities have very different origins (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 22). On one hand, sustainable city originated under the intention of strengthening resource conservation and future viability. Later on, at a global level, especially on Western societies, started considering the inclusion of different population groups, as well as the legitimization of decisions, and aspects of quality of life. On the other hand, the Smart City's origins recall the desire of greater efficiency of self-controlled urban systems and infrastructures. The core at Smart City's idea was focused on the expansion and use of ICT, and early concepts did not consider social or ecological aspects (Allwinkle and Cruickshank, 2011). Therefore, one of the greatest progresses to date is the combination of urban smartness and environmental sustainability. Nevertheless, these aspects do not consider data security

⁴ This ever-increasing could be, for example, related with further globalization of the financial system, climate change or the advancing digitalization (Deutscher Städtetag, 2015, p. 14)

and privacy. This could lead to the increase of vulnerability of certain population groups when they are forced to use smart technologies (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 23).

The sustainable urban development considers a five-pillar model of sustainability. This model includes the traditional ecological, socio-cultural, and economic aspects, while adding institutional and spatial sustainability (Hopfner and Zakrzewski, 2012).

For Abraham *et al.* (2017, pp. 23–25), *Smartness* is a qualitative target perspective for urban development that is not a characteristic of technologies, but more of the design approaches, strategies and projects conceived by people. For them, Smart City strategies and projects have the goal to contribute to the improvement in the quality of urban life. To do so, it is vital the inclusion of broad stakeholder groups in the design and decision on the objectives and content of Smart City strategies (participatory governance).

The Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft (ZTG) (in English: Center for Technology and Society) divides the Smart City research in seven areas: climate and energy (1), land use and consumption patterns (2), mobility and space (3), social movements, technology, conflicts (4), sustainability (5), participation (6), and governance and innovation (7) (Idem., pp. 30–38).

In conclusion, the intersection between sustainability and smartness in terms of urban development, represents an evolution. The search for balanced urban development is seeking for the equilibrium which ensures that technological advancements contribute to efficiency, social inclusivity, ecological responsibility, and overall resilience in the face of evolving urban challenges.

3.2.3 Examples of Smart City implementation

Cities throughout the globe are advocating to apply smart technologies. Though, the Smart City concept has been mainly implemented into the existing configurations of urban governance and the built environment, rather than constructing new cities from scratch, which are exceptions (Shelton, Zook and Wiig, 2015, p.13-27).

The motives, development and objectives of a Smart City strategy are very diverse. Their fields of action and how they are evaluated also depend on the respective city's understanding of the term or show the need for innovative solutions in individual areas (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 14–17). Some common objectives include:

"[...] improving living conditions, conserving resources, strengthening resilience, security and the competitiveness of cities [...] participation in the Smart City megatrend or the opportunity to apply for research or funding. [...] Cities with ambitious, comprehensive Smart City strategies quickly gain an image as pioneering cities, which gives them further advantages when it comes to attracting projects and events." (Ibidem.)

3.2.3.1 Smart City approach in the European context

At the European Union (EU), the smart cities topic was first taken as part of the Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan), whose objective was to test new technologies in cities and how they would have a positive impact on energy efficiency. In consequence, the Directorate-General for Energy launched the "Smart Cities and Communities" initiative in 2011, that later included mobility and ICT (EurActiv, 2014). This led to the Horizon 2020 funding program, where the EU funded three European Smart City lighthouse projects: Copenhagen, Vienna, and London (Mörsch, 2015). Vienna, for example, formulated explicit Smart City strategies. Copenhagen, on the other hand, integrated the Smart City idea into overarching concepts. And Barcelona developed a strategy for the classification, promotion, and networking of Smart City projects, adding the mobility master plan that serves as a framework for smart transport development. These cities often link their Smart City

strategies to higher goals than just the use of ICT, especially related with environment protection and improvement of the quality of life. Diverse stakeholders are also involved in the development and implementation of the of the Smart City strategies. This has led in some cases to the cooperation between private (companies, associations, civil society, etc.) with public institutions (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 15–17).

3.2.3.2 Smart City approach examples in Latin America

In emerging countries, the aspect of urban safety plays a greater role internationally than in Europe and the English-speaking world (Idem., p. 19). For example, in Brazilian Smart City strategies, the ICT is justified by the search of sustainability, as well as the better integration and management of urban services (Weiss, Bernardes and Consoni, 2017, pp. 2–10). Similarly to certain projects in Europe, the Smart City projects are implemented within the framework of international cooperation networks with the private sector, research institutes and universities (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 19–20). The unstable political situation in Brazilian cities has led to high crime rates. Therefore, some smart cities strategies are implementing digital systems that are intended for control and public surveillance. Such is the case in Curitiba, Sao Paulo or Porto Alegre (Ruiz and Tigre, 2014, p. 85-95) (Singer, 2012). Another example is the implementation of the Control Center of the city of Rio de Janeiro, whose software monitors in real-time meteorological, crime, traffic and emergency data and receives live cam feeds from all over the city. With this data collected by sensors and new communication channels, forecasts of natural disasters are created and made available to the community centers so that population can be warned (Prefeitura do Rio de Janeiro, 2012, pp. 64–67).

In Mexico, during this twenty-first century, different states have adopted Smart City technologies and approaches. Some examples are Mexico City, Puebla, Querétaro, and Jalisco (Guarneros Olmos, 2023). In 2015, Merida City started implementing digital tools that started the city's technological transformation, especially regarding Smart Mobility (Fernández, 2015). (See section 6.3.4).

These examples aim to illustrate that the current Smart City discourse has a focus on the increasing possibilities of networking due to technological development. The scope, impact and type of objectives (economic, social or ecological) depends on the concrete implementation of each city (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 14).

4 Mobility within an Urban Context

Mobility refers to the ability with which individuals, goods or information can move within a given system or environment. It includes not only the physical act of transportation but includes the overall accessibility and flexibility of movement. Though mobility includes diverse modes of transportation, it also extends beyond to consider factors such as urban planning, connectivity, accessibility, flexibility, and the use of technology to facilitate movement (Modeshift, 2023).

4.1 Sustainable Transport as a component of Mobility

4.1.1 Definition of Transport

Transport is a subset of mobility. Transport refers to the movement of people or goods from one place to another. It involves physical means and infrastructure used for the movement, including vehicles, roads, railways, airports, and ports. It also considers regulations and logistics. Transport has three main types: land, water and air. Each type uses specific vehicles to carry out the movement. Table 1 represents the Main Passenger Modal Options (Rodrigue, 2020).

Table 1: Main Passenger Modal Options

Air	Land		Water
Planes	Road	Rail	Ferry
° Charter	Car	Intercity	Cruise
° Scheduled	Taxi	HSR	
	Van/Bus	Transit	
	Motorcycle	°Subway	
	Micromobility	°Commuter	
	Walking	°LRT	
		°Monorail	

Source: Elaborated by author based on Jean-Paul Rodrigue (2020)

Regarding Road’s Modal Options, Rodrigue (Ibidem.) highlights that there is a range of motorized and non-motorized options that user may opt for short distances, depending on affordability, availability, convenience, and comfort. Though automobiles have emerged as a predilect form of transport due to its flexibility and convenience, it also contributes to congestion in urban areas. When talking about Taxi, it can be both for-hire services or ride-sharing ones. Nevertheless, strategies promoting sustainable transport systems point out the importance of walking, cycling, and emerging forms of personal mobility. These include micro mobility, a term used to refer to small electric or human-powered transportation devices.

4.1.2 Sustainable Transport Context

According to the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2023), urban planning, transport systems, and access to information, amongst others, are relevant issues to sustainable urban development. The 1992 United Nation’s Earth Summit, as well as the outcome document Agenda 21, were the first platforms to recognize the role of transport in sustainable development. In 1997, the UN General Assembly already predicted that over the next twenty years, transportation would be the major driving force behind a world with an increasing demand for energy. Nowadays, transport is the largest end-use of energy in developed countries and the fastest growing in emerging ones. The Johannesburg Plan of Implementation (JPOI) resulted from the 2002 World Summit on Sustainable Development, shows diverse anchor points for sustainable transport, including infrastructure, public transport systems, networks for goods delivery, and transportation in terms of affordability, efficiency, and convenience. This would have an impact and improvement in urban air quality and health, while reducing the greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) (United Nations

Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023b).

At the 2012 United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio +20), world leaders recognized the central role of transport and mobility in regard with sustainable development. Sustainable transport can achieve better integration of the economy while respecting the environment, improving social equity, health, and resilience of cities, as well as urban-rural linkages and productivity. Later in 2014, the UN Secretary-General established a High-Level Advisory Group on Sustainable Transport (HLAG-ST) that represented all modes of transport including road, aviation, rail, ferry, marine, and urban public transport providers. HLAG-ST submitted in 2016 the “Mobilizing Sustainable Transport for Development”. Recently, in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, sustainable transport has been mainstreamed across several SDGs related to food security, health, economic growth, energy, infrastructure, and cities and human settlements. According to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), transport plays a major role in achieving the Paris Agreement, due to the growth projections of global GHG energy-related with transport (Ibidem.).

4.1.3 Definition of Sustainable Transport

The HLAG-ST (2016, p. 6) has defined sustainable transport as:

“[...] the provision of services and infrastructure for the mobility of people and goods— advancing economic and social development to benefit today’s and future generations—in a manner that is safe, affordable, accessible, efficient, and resilient, while minimizing carbon and other emissions and environmental impacts.”

HLAG-ST considers Transport as a mean to allow people access to meet their needs: jobs, markets, social interaction, education, and other services and amenities that can contribute to a healthy and fulfilled life. Transport should prioritize people, their quality of life, as well as safety and social equity. HLAG-ST suggest that through sustainable transport, there can be a significant progress on the SDGs and the Paris Climate Agreement (Ibidem.).

4.1.4 Transport Transition in Mexico

The transport sector in Mexico is one of the main sources of GHG and short-lived climate pollutants. In the recent years, in addition to contributing to global warming, GHG also generates significant impacts on the health of population. Therefore, the Ley General de Cambio Climático (LGCC) (in English: General Law on Climate Change) has prioritized their mitigation. Mexico’s Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC)⁵ contains an expanded ambition in transportation sector, following the commitments established at the United Nations Climate Change conference in Glasgow (COP 26). Mexico committed to accelerate efforts in Alliance with private sector and cities, for electric mobility. Mexico is working to consolidate the National Strategy for Electric Mobility to achieve these objectives and implement fair and safe mechanisms, in addition to promoting the transformation of public transport, which is the sector with greatest social impact. Additional to promoting electromobility, Mexico committed to strengthen the regulations regarding vehicle energy efficiency. The goal is to reduce the carbon footprint of the vehicle fleet and encourage the transition to more efficient vehicles and the promotion of clean transportation programs. Among the measures, Mexico has also considered the expansion and rehabilitation of national rail network, which allows to reduce GHG emissions, due to its greater energy efficiency when transporting goods and people (Gobierno de México, 2022b, pp. 11–12). Finally, the strategy for the transport sector highlights an improvement in linking urban planning with climate change criteria and the recovery of public space for pedestrians. The strategy considers a planning oriented to efficient public transport systems and alternative non-motorized transportation systems. These actions support compliance with the GHG target (Idem., p.12).

⁵ Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) is a climate action plan to cut emissions and adapt to climate impacts. Every Party at the [Paris Agreement](#) is required to set an NDC and must update them every five years (United Nations Climate Action, 2023a).

4.2 Definition of Mobility

Mobility is a key element in the urbanization and development of any urban settlement. It impacts in the life quality of its inhabitants and their well-being (Mela and Girardi, 2022, pp. 1–2). Mobility and its associated infrastructure shape the urban form of cities, specifically within the spatial imprint defined by roads, transport systems, spaces, and buildings. In 2005, approximately 7.5 billion trips were made in cities throughout the world every day. In 2050, the passenger-kilometers traveled as in the year 2000 might be three to four times more (UN-Habitat, 2023).

As mentioned before, mobility is also related to the ability with which individuals, goods, or information can move within a given system or environment (Modeshift, 2023). The Mobility Lab⁶ (2018) highlights that mobility is also based on having transportation options and the quality of these. The Mobility Lab team defined the quality of transportation based on three components: time, affordability, and safety.

In order to reach sustainable mobility, current mobility challenges call for a paradigm shift in the urban planning setting. This should encourage compact cities and mixed-land use as a form to increase accessibility and reduce the need for general transportation. To do so, it is vital to understand that the purpose of mobility is to access destinations, activities, services and goods. Therefore, urban planning must be resident-centered so that functional endpoints (reasons for travel) are as close as possible to each other. This approach is more efficient than merely adding urban transport infrastructure to increase movement. On the contrary, the closeness between the functional endpoints will reduce both distances and transportation needs (UN-Habitat, 2023).

Parallel, it is necessary to change the current preference towards private motor vehicles into more sustainable mobility concepts, including public transport systems with a high passenger capacity, high area coverage, and low energy use and carbon emissions. In order to do so, cities are required to develop public transport systems that are attractive, accessible, and affordable. Cities should procure that the transport systems are within reach (geographical and financial) of all residents, and special focus on the most vulnerable economically. Since most trips involve several modes of transport, cities should also provide multi-modal transport systems and consider modal integration an important component of the urban mobility strategy. Special focus should be placed on the “last mile access”⁷, to allow residents an easy access to the public transportation system. Urban space needs should also be rethought to optimize the flow of traffic and increase the use of non-motorized transport (Ibidem.).

Different approaches towards mobility have taken place. The following sub-sections will focus on three main mobility approaches: sustainable mobility, Smart Mobility, and Active Mobility.

4.2.1 Sustainable Mobility

A defining factor for the future of mobility is to have a long-term perspective focused on sustainability (Mohieldin and Vandycke, 2017). Since 2017, sustainable mobility is a concept that has emerged as a standard in the international transport community. In order for mobility to be sustainable, four policy goals should be achieved: universal access, efficiency, safety, and green mobility (Sustainable Mobility for All, 2022). Mohieldin and Vandycke (2017) define the vision for sustainable mobility based on four global goals: equitable access (1), security and safety (2), efficiency (3), pollution and climate responsiveness (4). Under this perspective, sustainable mobility will include a better

⁶ Mobility Lab is a program of Arlington County, Virginia, funded partly by grants from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT), the Virginia Department of Transportation (VDOT) and the Virginia Department of Rail and Public Transportation (DRPT) (Mobility Lab, 2018)

⁷ Last mile access refers to the trips taken from public transport to the journey destination, while first mile access has to do with the trips taken from point of origin to high frequency transport (Romm *et al.*, 2022, pp. 1–3).

provision of infrastructure and services to support the movement of people and goods.

To shift into sustainable transport, it is necessary an increased local, national and international funding and climate support. Institutional investors could play a role in accelerating the shift to zero-carbon mobility options. To encompass changes in zero-carbon technologies, policy measures should include establishing national, regional, and city targets for electrifying transportation modes, offering financial incentives, establishing zero-emission zones in urban and regional areas, and formulating policies that foster behavioural change. Businesses could also enhance the shift by including original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) committed to the electrification of the sectors also by the diversification in the models and segments that provide economic opportunities for new players, such as start-ups and small/medium-sized companies that develop e-mobility solutions (Global Climate Change Action, 2020, p. 2-3).

4.2.2 Smart Mobility

Smart Mobility is a concept that aims to make transportation and traffic services more sustainable by increasing user-friendliness and accessibility. Smart Mobility uses the potential of the intensive information exchange and constant growing connectivity between people and machines, with the objective to create user-oriented transport systems and services. Some well-known mobility innovations that take advantage of the potential are the autonomous vehicles and the private driving service Uber (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 33).

Smart Mobility includes anything related with mobility in the Smart City, including:

“[...] the sustainability of the transport network, integrated platforms, sustainable, intelligent and cooperative vehicle technologies, sustainable and safe environment, behavioural economics, e-participation, or crowdsourcing.”

(Müller-Eie and Kosmidis, 2023 quoting Maldonado Silveira Alonso Munhoz *et al.*, 2020).

4.2.2.1 Smart Mobility Objectives

Within the context of Smart Cities, Smart Mobility objectives includes three key drivers: mixed-modal access; prioritized clean and non-motorized options, and integrated ICT (See Figure 5: Smart Cities Wheel) (Cohen, 2012). Other objectives related with Smart Mobility are the improvement in the transfer speed and increased safety, as well as the reduction of traffic congestion, transfer costs, and air and noise pollution (Mezei and Lázanyi, 2018, p. 369). Indirectly, smart transport can contribute to the increase in the quality of life among citizens (Silva, Khan and Han, 2018).

4.2.2.2 Smart Mobility Technologies

Technology will be the guiding principle of mobility in the future. A larger amount of data and connectivity can translate into more efficient and convenient mobility. These opportunities for emerging countries could lead to surpass the existing legacy technologies and practices. Some notable examples are the advances in analytics, automation and the Internet of Things⁸ (IoT), that are showing promising progress in reducing consumption, specially of energy (Mohieldin and Vandycke, 2017). Technology investments are desirable for future Smart Mobility, in order to make more efficient the integration of transport infrastructure that configures, protects, repairs, and adapts itself (Nam and Pardo, 2011, p. 286). However, it is vital for all Smart Mobility solutions to determine people's actual mobility needs (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 33).

Smart technologies provide institutional and official bodies the possibility to link demographic and economic developments with the associated short-term traffic

⁸ Internet of Things (IoT) is the collective network of linked devices and the technology that facilitates communication between themselves and the cloud. Nowadays there are billions of devices connected to internet, whose sensors collect data and respond intelligently to users (Amazon Web Services, 2023).

behavioural changes. This allows to respond to people's requirements at short notice in the context of participatory planning based on feedback. This also facilitates the integration into mobility management systems (for example, via floating car data, apps, or car-2-x infrastructure⁹). This information serves to improve traffic planning and transport services through powerful models and simulations. Understood as a functioning system, all the aspects associated with Smart Mobility (including smart energy, people, etc.) are a supportive environment for the implementation of sustainable, resource-efficient, and climate-friendly modes of transportation. The goal is to integrate all transport services and modes, in order to reduce access barriers and increase the exchange of information (Idem., p. 34).

In the international area of mobility and spaces, the focus is on the sustainability of private mobility and commercial transport. Therefore, Smart Mobility solutions are gaining prominence, especially concrete applications which include new modes of transport that use new technologies (such as electric bikes, ridesharing, etc.). The optimization of existing transport modes is also important, for example, when integrating booking systems or the municipal promotion of intelligent mobility management takes place. Here, the focus is centered on multimodal and multifunctional mobility services, electromobility, participatory planning processes and integrated infrastructure service providers (Ibidem.). For the development and infrastructure planning, many projects are based on geoinformation systems, mainly those related with energy and transport (Idem., p. 36).

In metropolis, mobility services provided to users on smartphones have already started a move away towards shared vehicle usage, rather than the traditional vehicle ownership. Technology enables services like car-sharing, ride-hailing, and carpooling. Connected and autonomous vehicle technology could help optimize roadway use, which could translate in the potential saving of billions for future infrastructure expansion (Mohieldin and Vandycke, 2017).

4.2.2.3 Mobility as a Service and Mobility on Demand Potential

The urban mobility trends Mobility as Service (MaaS) and Mobility on Demand (MoD) are growing in popularity. These models are based on the idea that mobility is a service that is rented and paid for, despite the chosen means of transport (sharing car, bicycle, public transport, autonomous shuttle bus, or e-scooter) (Sengupta, 2022).

4.2.2.4 Risks in implementing Smart Mobility technologies

The main risk associated with new technology is the fact that the car remains the core element of the future of mobility. This could lead to congested cities that have a dearth of tax revenues to manage and maintain roads, and with a massive job loss due to automation. That is the reason why decision-makers should focus on actions to avoid unnecessary physical movement of people through the use of technology, rather than just focusing in improving mobility and shifting towards public modes of transportation (Mohieldin and Vandycke, 2017).

4.2.2.5 Examples of Smart Mobility initiatives

Every city has its own mobility needs and challenges, based on diverse elements that include density, existing infrastructure, climate, topography, etc. Though cities can learn from each other, it is vital that each develops its own benchmarks and targets among the areas of need and opportunity (Cohen, 2012).

⁹ In Car-2-x infrastructure, vehicles exchange information with each other and with the infrastructure, using radio communication. This information is transmitted via a standardized message to their surroundings, including data such as speed, position and other status. Afterwards, the infrastructure and the receiving vehicles can use this information to enhance and enrich the mapping of the existing environment. The complementary process is called i-2-v, where infrastructure transmits information to the vehicle (Vector, 2023).

Copenhague, Denmark, is a great example of the efforts carried out to promote and prioritize cycling. In 1981 the city developed its first cycling plan, that has evolved the cycling and mixed-modal objectives since 2002. However, these efforts have been based on data and information. Copenhagen has measured cycling and mixed-modal use for decades. Based on the data, the city has determined a target indicator: to achieve 50% of all trips to work or school by bike by 2015. By 2009, they had already achieved 37%. The city has also collaborated with MIT in the creation of the Copenhagen Wheel, a hybrid bike wheel that leverages sensors in a bike wheel that can monitor traffic congestion, road conditions and monitor pollution in real time (Ibidem.).

Maas Global a startup funded in Helsinki, Finland, is also a great example when talking about MaaS. They designed the “Whim” application whose objective is to allow citizens to move around the city in the most simple and economical way possible. This is achieved by offering to connect through different means of transport (Velco, 2023).

At the government level, French state is also a good example. Municipalities and national stakeholders have taken advantage of the stakes and opportunities of this new form of mobility (MaaS), that fully integrates Smart Mobility in a long-term transformation of Smart Cities. The National Company of the French Railways (SNCF) and the RATP have set up local initiatives that have been supported by municipalities. In 2018 Keolis (a subsidiary of SNCF) developed the “Star” application, where the cities of Dijon and Rennes could combine bicycle, bus, carpooling and metro, while indicating in real time the availability of parking spaces throughout the city. Similar applications have been developed in other French cities, such as “TAC mobilités” in Annemasse, and “Moovizy” in Mulhouse and Saint Etienne. These offer travelers a single application where they can prepare itineraries, consult next passages of the diverse modes of transport, and search for timetables (Ibidem.).

4.2.3 Active Mobility in Urban Areas

4.2.3.1 Active Mobility Definition

Active Mobility, also known as soft mobility, is defined as the use of non-motorized mobility (i.e. walking and cycling) for transport, either solely or in combination with public transport. Contrary to exercise or sports, Active Mobility requires less time and motivation, is convenient as a mode of transport and as a way of exercise and is economically affordable. The increase of Active Mobility supports public health objectives and goals in transport planning (Gerike *et al.*, 2016). The increase of Active Mobility reduces the consumption of space for transport infrastructure, energy use, air and noise pollution. In general, it improves quality of urban life (Pendyala, Bhat and International Association for Travel Behaviour Research, 2012, p. 28). Active Mobility friendly spatial settings should consider the principles of density, destination’s accessibility and design, distance to public transport and diversity (Cervero and Kockelman, 1997). On the other hand, perceived lack of traffic safety is an important disincentive for Active Mobility (De Geus *et al.*, 2012).

The intention to use certain transports can be influenced through attitudes, habits, perceived behavioural control, and norms (social and personal) (Koszowski *et al.*, 2019). Among the factors that determine the Active Mobility behaviour are sociodemographic characteristics, such as income or car ownership (Handy, Van Wee and Kroesen, 2014). Sociopsychological factors also play a role. These include preferences, attitudes, habits, or norms (Bauman *et al.*, 2012). Finally, sociogeographic factors that are involved include climate, topography, the built environment, or transport systems (Handy, Van Wee and Kroesen, 2014).

Arellana *et al.* (2020) define the walkability of a city based on the hierarchy of walking needs proposed by Alfonzo (2005). The walkability is determined and can be evaluated by the sidewalk condition, traffic safety and security, comfort, and attractiveness (See Figure 6).

Figure 6: Walkability Evaluation

Source: Arellana *et al.*, 2020, p. 189

4.2.3.2 Contextualizing Active Mobility concept

The twenty-first century has been characterized by a global pursuit of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban settlements (United Nations Department for Economic and Social Affairs, 2023, p. 34). In this context, Active Mobility has become a prominent trend because it encourages physical activity, a healthier lifestyle, and environmentally friendly transportation options (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p. 1,2). Balanced and integrated development of all the diverse transportation modes is also a goal of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) (Rupprecht Consult, 2019, p. 19). UN Habitat (2023) highlights the need to rethink urban space in order to optimize the flow of traffic, while increasing and encouraging the use of non-motorized transport, such as cycling or pedestrian movement. To achieve the goal, streets should be adapted with walkways, crossings, cycling lanes, and transport junctions for different transport modes. Access to the range of public transport system and its extension on both, macro (city-region) and micro (neighborhood) levels.

Based on data from the year 2015, the International Transport Forum | OECD (2021) reveals that urban mobility generates 40 per cent of all CO₂ emissions from the movement of people, while non-urban transport represents the remaining 60 per cent. Out of this, 75 % of all emissions from urban passenger transport is generated by private cars. From a sustainability perspective, according to the International Council on Clean Transportation (2020, p.12), approximately 70 % of CO₂ emission reductions that are needed to meet the 1.5°C target of Paris Agreement can be achieved through changes in technologies (such as electrification and efficiency improvement), while 15 % can be reached with changes in behaviour, such as reductions in distance traveled through the expansion of teleworking, integrated land use and transport planning, as well as shifts to more sustainable modes, such as walking, public transport and cycling (Global Climate Change Action, 2021, p. 5).

4.2.3.3 Examples of Active Mobility initiatives

Some cities that show that high shares of Active Mobility are feasible, are located in Spain and the Netherlands. In the case of Bilbao, Spain, walking shares more than 50% of all the trips. The cities of Groningen or Eindhoven, in the Netherlands, have cycling shares of up to 44% (Gerike *et al.*, 2016). Other cities that have promoted and/or implemented strategies to achieve Active Mobility are Helsinki, Copenhagen, Zurich, and Hamburg. Helsinki city is developing a network of walkable and interconnected neighbourhoods, to prioritize active transport and make all activities to make on daily travel by foot or bicycle. Copenhagen on the other hand, has been working towards walkable cities since the 1960s, when they created areas exclusive to pedestrians. Copenhagen's transformation represents a shift in understanding that promoting pedestrian paths for walking and active transport can be the baseline to improve mobility and building a better city for its inhabitants. Zurich is another example on walkability: 34% of the trips are made on foot or by bike. Zurich's plans to strengthen active transport began in 1996 with the History Commitment, that stated that no new parking spaces could be built in the city unless they were replacing old ones. This translated in a reduction and limit to the use of cars in the city. In the case of Hamburg, the plan is to dedicate 40% of the city's land to green public spaces. This so-called Green Network has the objective to represent that large cities can be walkable and designed for people (Caccia, 2019).

Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that walkability and Active Mobility are not exclusive of the global north. Cities in the global south, and specially in Latin America, have also been implementing Active Mobility strategies. Cities such as Mexico City, Merida, Guadalajara in Mexico, Bogotá in Colombia, and Buenos Aires in Argentina, have implemented diverse strategies to promote cycling. For example, financial incentives, new policies, air quality monitoring, and education programs (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 21).

4.2.3.4 Benefits of implementing Active Mobility

Sustainability

Walking and biking are the least carbon-intensive means of transport. United Nations (2023b) suggests that if the end destination is at a short-distance reach, citizens should consider the weakly increase of walking or biking. On the other hand, if the distance is too far for this means of transport, public transportation is a sustainable alternative. The simple shift from cars to public transport can reduce up to 2.2 tons of carbon emissions annually per individual. Another alternative to car use is the carpooling, which can result in up to 1 ton of carbon emissions reduced. Going car-free can reduce the annual carbon footprint by up to 3.6 tons. United Nations (2023b) also recommends the use of shared modes of transportation (bike, scooter, or car services), for they have a higher per-unit utilization and could reduce the need for net new manufacturing. Therefore, by using share modes services, the manufacturing emissions can also decrease.

Health

Cycling is related to fitness and health for elder people due to its lower impact on hips and joints than other cardiovascular activities such as running. It also helps people stay connected to others. Tsunoda *et al.* (2015) suggest that there is a positive association between frequency of bicycle and motor vehicle travel and physical activity, social networks, and mental status. Their analysis also revealed that extending the travel area through the use of transportation modes might imply health benefits. Evaluating the transportation mode usage could also improve screening and assistance strategies for individuals experiencing physical or mental frailty or loneliness.

Social Equity

Walking grants universal accessibility, for anyone can be a pedestrian despite their age, gender, ethnicity or socioeconomic status. Therefore, urban spaces that promote pedestrian activity could help diminish the social inequalities that are caused by unequal access to other transportation means (Curtis and Scheurer, 2010).

5 Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach

5.1 Recap of the previous chapters

In order to understand how the Smart City approach can enhance Active Mobility, it is important to begin with a recapitulation of the preceding chapters where the concepts Smart City, Mobility, Sustainable Mobility, Smart Mobility and Active Mobility were presented. Table 2 provides a summary of the characteristics of the concepts discussed in the previous sections.

The Smart City Approach rises as a strategy to address the challenges faced by rapid urbanization. It enhances ICT to enhance urban living conditions, conserve resources, and increase resilience (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 14–17). Nevertheless, Smart City initiatives should be based on a holistic integration of diverse urban fields, including energy, mobility, urban planning, and participatory governance (Rohde and Loew, 2011, p. 5). In order to align with sustainability goals, Smart City concepts should comply to principles such as compact, mixed-use, and integrated urban planning modes (Deutscher Städtetag, 2015, p. 6).

Mobility focuses on the movement of individuals, goods, and information within urban context (Modeshift, 2023). Under this understanding, sustainable transport is an important component that promotes safe, affordable, accessible, efficient and resilient mobility with a reduction on environmental impacts (HLAG-ST, 2016, p. 6). To achieve sustainable mobility, users need to shift preferences from private motor vehicles to more sustainable options, such as the use of public transport systems, multi-modal transport, and the optimization of urban space to promote non-motorized transport (UN-Habitat, 2023).

Smart Mobility takes advantage of the potential of information exchange and connectivity to create user-oriented transport systems. Autonomous vehicles and ride-sharing services are innovative services that, in addition to the adoption of smart technologies, allow real-time response to changing patterns of traffic behaviour, and contributes to the implementation of sustainable and climate-friendly modes of transport (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 33-34).

Active Mobility uses non-motorized vehicles (such as walking and cycling) and is considered a sustainable mode of transportation (Gerike *et al.*, 2016). Urban spaces need to be rethink in order to optimize traffic flow and create pedestrian-friendly infrastructure that ensures accessibility to public transport networks (UN-Habitat, 2023). Active Mobility reduces the consumption of space and energy, while bringing benefits in terms of health and sustainability (Mela and Girardi, 2022, pp. 1–2).

The symbiosis between Sustainability, the Smart City approach, Smart Mobility, and Active Mobility resides in their common pursuit of creating urban environments that are inclusive, resilient, and environmentally sustainable. Therefore, a coordinated strategy should involve integrating smart technologies, sustainable transport systems, and Active Mobility solutions within the broader framework of urban planning to address challenges faced by rapid urbanization. This with the final goal to contribute to a sustainable future for the generations to come.

5.2 Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach

In Table 2, the concepts of Sustainable Development, Sustainable Mobility and Transport, Smart City, Active Mobility, and Smart Mobility are explored.

In order to enhance Active Mobility through the Smart City approach, it is important to understand its objectives and components.

In the case of Active Mobility, its goals are the use non-motorized vehicles (i.e., walking and cycling) for transport (solely or combined with public transport) (Gerike *et al.*, 2016). Active Mobility aims to encourage physical activity, a healthier lifestyle, and environmentally friendly transportation options (Mela and Girardi, 2022, pp. 1–2). Contrary to exercise or sports, Active Mobility requires less time and motivation, is convenient as a mode of transport and as a way of exercise and is economically affordable. The increase in Active Mobility supports public health objectives and goals in transport planning, reduces space consumption for transport infrastructure, energy use, and air and noise pollution, and promotes social equity (Gerike *et al.*, 2016) (Pendyala, Bhat and International Association for Travel Behaviour Research, 2012, p. 28). To enhance Active Mobility, diverse factors play a role. In an urban context, these include:

- The spatial setting: density, accessibility, design, distance to public transport, and diversity (Cervero and Kockelman, 1997)
- Infrastructure: walkways, crossings, cycling lanes, and transport junctions (UN-Habitat, 2023)
- Walkability: sidewalk condition, traffic safety, security, comfort, and attractiveness (Arellana *et al.*, 2020, p. 189)
- Attitudes, habits, perceived behavioural control, and norms (social and personal) (Koszowski *et al.*, 2019)
- Sociodemographic characteristics, sociopsychological, and socio-geographic factors (Handy, Van Wee and Kroesen, 2014)

From a policy perspective, additional conditions should be considered, including:

- The establishment of national, regional, and city targets for electrifying transportation modes, offering financial incentives, establishing zero-emission zones in urban and regional areas, and formulating policies that foster behavioural change (Global Climate Change Action, 2020, pp. 2–3).
- The role of Businesses on the shift by including original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) committed to the electrification of the sectors by the diversification in the models and segments that provide economic opportunities for new players, such as start-ups and small/medium-sized companies that develop e-mobility solutions (Ibidem.).

In most of these factors, Smart City and Smart Mobility approaches can play a role to enhance Active Mobility.

For example, in terms of the spatial setting in accessibility and distance to public transport, the Smart City approach can help implement an integrated transportation system where Smart Mobility solutions integrate diverse modes of transportation that create an efficient network. This network could include buses, trains, bicycles, as well as sharing mobility systems (Velco, 2023). Smart City technologies can also provide real-time information (Cohen, 2012) on public transportation schedules, traffic conditions, and alternative routes. Smart transportation systems can also optimize public transport routes based on the demand and address the "last-mile" challenge. This allows citizens to make informed decisions regarding their travel routes, as well as reducing congestion, bridging the gap between home and public transport hubs, and improving overall accessibility. This translates into a reduction in travel time and a more attractive view towards public transportation. In terms of the spatial setting of density, the Smart City approach encourages mixed-use development (Deutscher Städtetag, 2015, p. 6), which optimizes land use and reduces the need for extensive commuting.

In terms of infrastructure and walkability, at walkways and crossings could implement smart public lighting and smart crosswalks, where intelligent lighting systems, pedestrian flow monitoring and smart crosswalks can be implemented. Through the use of motion sensors and cameras, lights can activate and adjust brightness as people approach, and monitor pedestrian flow in real-time (Chiradeja and Yoomak, 2023). This can enhance safety and energy efficiency. And the data collected can also be analyzed to optimize the walkways and crossings design (Bennett, Coleman & Co. Ltd., 2023).

Regarding the cycling lanes, cyclist-friendly navigation apps and bike sharing systems can help promote cycling as a sustainable alternative for mobility (Sengupta, 2022), and in consequence, enhance Active Mobility. In both cases, cyclist could have real-time information on the availability of cycling lanes, parking spaces, traffic conditions (Cohen, 2012) and optimal routes.

From a policy perspective, regarding the establishment of zero-emission zones in urban and regional areas, Smart City technologies can implement geo-fences to create zero-emission zones that can be integrated with navigation systems to guide drivers through free-emission routes, as well as to monitor in real time through sensors and cameras to issue warnings or penalties (Spik, 2022).

Regarding financial incentives, public-private partnerships can be established to collaborate between government entities, the private sector and technology providers. This can be made through collaborative platforms where sharing of resources, expertise and data can be facilitated (McKinsey & Company, 2019). Finally, in terms of behavioural change initiatives, digital communication channels can be used to raise public awareness campaigns to communicate and educate the population about the benefits of Active Mobility, public transport, and electrification.

These are general examples that focus on the possibilities of Smart City approach to enhance Active Mobility. However, in the next section will be presented concrete examples.

5.3 Examples of Active Mobility enhanced by Smart City approaches

Some concrete examples where Smart City approach has enhanced Active Mobility have been discussed in the previous sections. Such is the case of Copenhagen in section 4.2.2.5.

Copenhaguen, Denmark, is a great example of how the Smart City approach can enhance Active Mobility. The city has long been involved in ICT-oriented Smart City projects, which include the establishment of digital infrastructure, the dissemination of public data and the expansion of smart buildings (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 16). Copenhagen also attaches great importance to ecological concerns and links the Smart City concept to this central self-image (Idem., p. 15). In 1981 Copenhagen developed its first cycling plan that evolved the cycling and mixed-modal objectives since 2002. Nevertheless, these efforts have been based on data and information. The city has measured cycling and mixed modal use for decades, and based on the data they determined a target indicator: to achieve 50% of all trips to work or school by bike by 2015. By 2009 they had achieved 37% (Cohen, 2012). In 2012, Copenhaguen proposed the climate plan “Copenhagen 2025” that embedded Smart City ideas with the goal to achieve CO₂ neutrality (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 16). The city has also collaborated with MIT in the creation of the Copenhagen Wheel, a hybrid bike wheel that leverages sensors in a bike wheel that can monitor traffic congestion, road conditions and monitor pollution in real time (Cohen, 2012).

The previous examples have focused on the possibilities of Smart City approach to enhance Active Mobility. However, the scope, impact and type of objectives (economic, social or ecological) depends on the concrete implementation of each city (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 14). The solutions, targets and benchmarks should be based on the specific mobility needs and challenges, based on elements such as density, existing infrastructure, climate, topography, etc. (Cohen, 2012).

Table 2: Summary and comparison among concepts:

Sustainable Development, Sustainable Mobility and Transport, Smart City, Active Mobility, and Smart Mobility.

Source: Elaborated by Author, 2023. Based on Chapters 3 & 4.

	Sustainable Development	Sustainable Mobility and Transport
Definition	Sustainable Development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.	Mobility: ability with which individuals, goods, or information can move within a given system or environment. Sustainable mobility is based on four global goals: equitable access (1), security and safety (2), efficiency (3), pollution and climate responsiveness (4). Sustainable transport is the provision of services and infrastructure for the mobility of people and goods in a manner that is safe, affordable, accessible, efficient, and resilient while minimizing carbon and other emissions and environmental impacts.
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To hold global temperature increase to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. - Global pursuit of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban settlements. - reduce nations' global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to hold temperature increase¹ and reduce the risks and impacts of climate change. - To strengthen resource conservation and future viability. - The inclusion of different population groups, as well as the legitimization of decisions and aspects of quality of life. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable Mobility should encourage compact cities and mixed-land use as a form to increase accessibility and reduce the need for general transportation. - An improvement in urban air quality and health while reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) - Better integration of the economy while respecting the environment, improving social equity, health, and resilience of cities, as well as urban-rural linkages and productivity. - Advancing economic and social development to benefit today and future generations. - To develop public transport systems that are attractive, accessible, and affordable. - Transport systems that are within reach (geographical and financial) of all residents - Balanced and integrated development of all the diverse transportation modes - Modal integration as a component of the urban mobility strategy. Special focus should be placed on the "last mile access" to allow residents easy access to the public transportation system. - To optimize traffic flow while increasing and encouraging the use of non-motorized transport, such as cycling or pedestrian movement. - To include better infrastructure and services to support the movement of people and goods.
Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecological, sociocultural, and economic aspects. - Institutional and spatial sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Walking, cycling, and emerging forms of personal mobility (including micro-mobility - a term for small electric or human-powered transportation devices) as components of sustainable transport systems. - Mobility and its associated infrastructure: the spatial imprint defined by roads, transport systems, spaces, and buildings. - Transportation options and the quality of these based on three components: time, affordability, and safety. - Transport physical means (vehicles) and infrastructure used for the movement, including vehicles, roads, railways, airports, and ports - Regulations and logistics. Transport has three main types: land, water and air. - Range of motorized and non-motorized options that users may opt for short distances, depending on affordability, availability, convenience, and comfort.
Elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Physical act of transportation, overall accessibility, and flexibility of movement. - Modes of transportation, urban planning, connectivity, accessibility, flexibility, and the use of technology to facilitate movement. - Infrastructure, public transport systems, networks for goods delivery - Transportation in terms of affordability, efficiency, and convenience. - Local, national, and international funding and climate support.
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transport is the fastest-growing end-use of energy in emerging countries. - Urban mobility generates 40 percent of all CO2 emissions from the movement of people, while non-urban transport represents the remaining 60 percent. Out of this, 75 percent of all emissions from urban passenger transport are generated by private cars. - Transport sector contributes to global warming and GHG significantly impacts the population's health. - Change the current preference towards private motor vehicles into more sustainable mobility concepts, including public transport systems with a high passenger capacity, high area coverage, and low energy use and carbon emissions. - Institutional investors could play a role in accelerating the shift to zero-carbon mobility options.
Highlights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation: SDG, Paris Agreement, and New Urban Agenda 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Through sustainable transport, there can be significant progress on the SDGs and the Paris Agreement. Sustainable transport has been mainstreamed across several SDGs related to food security, health, economic growth, energy, infrastructure, and cities and human settlements. UN suggests walking or biking, using public transportation, carpooling, shared modes of transportation (bike, scooter, or car services). - Urban planning must be resident-centered so that functional endpoints (reasons for travel) are as close as possible to each other. On the contrary, the closeness between the functional endpoints will reduce both distances and transportation needs.

Smart City	Active Mobility	Smart Mobility
<p>Smart City is an urban development approach proposed as an attempt to develop and implement ways for cities to deal with global energy consumption, CO2 emissions, and the growing population living in urban agglomerations through the use of ICT technologies.</p>	<p>Active mobility is defined as the use of non-motorized mobility (i.e., walking and cycling) for transport, either solely or in combination with public transport. Contrary to exercise or sports, active mobility requires less time and motivation, is convenient as a mode of transport and as a way of exercise and is economically affordable.</p>	<p>Smart Mobility includes anything related to mobility in the Smart City, including the sustainability of the transport network, integrated platforms, sustainable, intelligent, and cooperative vehicle technologies, sustainable and safe environment, behavioral economics, e-participation, or crowdsourcing. Smart mobility uses the potential of intensive information exchange and constantly growing connectivity between people and machines.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To overcome urban challenges with the new technical possibilities for the intelligent network of urban infrastructure and urban services - To improve and make the production and consumption of resources more efficient - To improve and increase the quality of life for citizens based on their needs - To move into a post-fossil society, where the consumption of resources is reduced, and the competitiveness of the local economy is permanently increasing - To improve sustainability in the city by promoting the integration and networking of various urban fields of action to realize ecological and social improvements. - To improve ecological (climate protection), social (education, inclusion, creative potential), and economic (competitiveness) sustainability at the city level. - To enhance sustainable economic growth and participatory governance. - To use ITC to enhance democratic debates to know what kind of city people want to live in. - To facilitate the development of networked communities by collecting collective knowledge to bring together citizens despite their backgrounds. - To impulse fair and democratic social structures - To promote equilibrium, which ensures that technological advancements contribute to efficiency, social inclusivity, ecological responsibility, and overall resilience in the face of evolving urban challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To encourage physical activity, a healthier lifestyle, and environmentally friendly transportation options. - Urban spaces promoting pedestrian activity can help diminish the social inequalities due to lack transport access. - Increasing active mobility supports public health objectives and goals in transport planning, reduces space consumption for transport infrastructure, energy use, and air and noise pollution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixed-modal access that prioritizes clean and non-motorized options and integrated ICT. - To make transportation and traffic services more sustainable by increasing user-friendliness and accessibility. - To improve transfer speed, increased safety, and reduced traffic congestion, transfer costs, and air and noise pollution - To contribute, indirectly, to the increase in the quality of life among citizens - More efficient and convenient mobility through higher data and connectivity. - The implementation of sustainable, resource-efficient, and climate-friendly modes of transportation. - To integrate all transport services and modes to reduce access barriers and increase the exchange of information. - To create user-oriented transport systems and services. - To focus on the sustainability of private mobility and commercial transport. - New modes of transport that use new technologies (such as electric bikes, ridesharing, etc.). - The optimization of existing transport modes - Focus on multimodal and multifunctional mobility services, electromobility, participatory planning processes, and integrated infrastructure service providers. - To reduce consumption, especially of energy.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart mobility, smart environment, smart people, smart governance, and smart living. - Computational, quantitative methodologies, and ICT to understand urban phenomena. - Companies from the ICT sector - Networks of ICT - Continuous learning and adaptation processes - Citizens' access to services and social and ecological sustainability - Human capital (i.e., qualified workforce), infrastructure capital (i.e., high-tech communications structures), social capital (i.e., diverse and open network connections), and entrepreneurial capital (e.g., creative and risk-taking business activities). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active mobility-friendly spatial settings that consider the principles of density, destination's accessibility and design, distance to public transport, and diversity. - Walkability is determined by the sidewalk condition, traffic safety, security, comfort, and attractiveness. - Attitudes, habits, perceived behavioral control, and norms (social and personal). - Factors determining active mobility behavior are sociodemographic characteristics, sociopsychological, and socio-geographic factors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analytics, automation, and the Internet of Things (IoT) - Smart mobility solutions to determine people's actual mobility needs. - Technology investments to make efficient the integration of transport infrastructure that configures, protects, repairs, and adapts itself - Data and information. - Mobility services provided to smartphone that promote a move away towards shared vehicle usage rather than traditional vehicle ownership. - Services like car-sharing, ride-hailing, and carpooling. - Connected and autonomous vehicle technology to optimize roadway use, which could translate into the potential saving of billions for future infrastructure expansion. - Smart technologies at institutional and official bodies that link demographic and economic developments with the associated short-term traffic behavioral changes. - Integration into mobility management systems (for example, via floating car data, apps, or car-2-x infrastructure). - Geoinformation systems, mainly those related to energy and transport, to develop infrastructure.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment in human capital, social capital, and traditional (transportation) and modern ICT infrastructures. - Vision and strategy for creating competitive cities and an approach for sustainable and inclusive cities. - Networking (of citizens, information, and urban infrastructure). - Targeted exploitation of ICT for networking, targeted use of the resulting networks and information flows. - ICT and social aspects (i.e., social capital and human capital) in addition to infrastructure. - Rapid action and efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For different transport modes, streets should be adapted with walkways, crossings, cycling lanes, and transport junctions. - Access to the range of public transport system and its extension on both macro (city-region) and micro (neighborhood) levels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobility as Service (MaaS) and Mobility on Demand (MoD), despite the chosen means of transport (sharing care, bicycle, public transport, autonomous shuttle bus, or e-scooter) - Sensors to monitor different indicators (climate, traffic, etc.) - Data and information to measure - Startups that develop applications that allow citizens to move around the city in the most simple and economically possible way by offering to connect through different means of transport. A single application to prepare itineraries, consult the next passages of the diverse modes of transport, and search for timetables.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No fixed understanding of the term. - Excessive mechanization and the emergence of new power structures. - Focus on technology and not on people. - Vested interests in Smart City initiatives. - Neglect of governance and participation perspective. - Adequate participation of the population in the decision-making process. - Technology-oriented approach without considering people's needs. - Corporations driving agenda into a market-oriented. - Economization of urban spaces and the possibility for companies to introduce data collection, control, and monitoring instruments. - Data security and privacy. - Technology could fail in emergency settings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of traffic safety is an important disincentive for active mobility. - Changes in zero-carbon technologies require policy measures that include establishing national, regional, and city targets for electrifying transportation modes, offering financial incentives, establishing zero-emission zones in urban and regional areas, and formulating policies that foster behavioral change. - Businesses could also enhance the shift by including original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) committed to the electrification of the sectors by the diversification in the models and segments that provide economic opportunities for new players, such as start-ups and small/medium-sized companies that develop e-mobility solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Car remains the core element of the future of mobility. This could lead to congested cities with a dearth of tax revenues to manage and maintain roads and a massive job loss due to automation. - Decision-makers should focus on actions to avoid unnecessary physical movement of people through the use of technology rather than just focusing on improving mobility and shifting towards public modes of transportation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tendency to equate a Smart City with a sustainable one as a consequence of the logical idea that self-controlling infrastructures and sensors can react flexibly to individual needs and save resources. - Combination of urban smartness and environmental sustainability. - Shift the power in ICT from business and government to communities and its inhabitants. - Alignment of the Smart City with sustainable urban development principles of compact, mixed-use, and use integrated urban planning model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cities in the global south, especially Latin America, have also implemented active mobility strategies, such as financial incentives, policies, monitoring, and education programs. - 15% of CO2 emission reductions that are needed to meet the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement can be achieved through changes in behavior. - Walking and biking are the least carbon-intensive means of transport. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology will be the guiding principle of mobility in the future. - Mobility innovations - Opportunities for emerging countries that lead to surpassing the existing legacy technologies and practices. - Every city has mobility needs and challenges based on diverse elements that include density, infrastructure, geography, etc. - Individual development of the city's benchmarks and targets among the areas of need and opportunity. - International focus is on the sustainability of private mobility and commercial transport, including new modes of transport that use new technologies (such as electric bikes, ridesharing, etc.). At promotion of intelligent mobility management, the focus is on multimodal and multifunctional mobility services, electromobility, participatory planning processes, and integrated infrastructure service providers.

6 Case Study: Merida City

In order to understand the case of study, this section will provide a general context on the national, regional, and local levels, as well as context in terms of Smart City initiatives and mobility. First, the national context of the Mexico country will be explored. Later on, the role that the Southeastern region plays and how it has shaped and influenced the Yucatan State, to finally understand Merida City specific context.

6.1 National Context: Mexico

6.1.1 Location and Geography of Mexico

Mexico is located in the southern part of North America (see Figure 7). Mexico's borders are the United States of America on the north, Guatemala and Belize on the south, The Gulf of Mexico and the Caribbean Sea to the east, and the Pacific Ocean to the west (SRE, 2013).

Mexico is the fourteenth largest country in the world. Its continental surface consists of 1'960,189 km², the Exclusive Economic Zone (with islands and territorial sea) is 3'149,920km², and the Extended Continental Shelf of 10,570km², giving a total of 5'120,679 km² (INEGI, 2024).

Figure 7: Mexico Map

Source: Elaborated by author based on Google | INEGI 2024

6.1.2 Political Division

Mexico's official name is Estados Unidos Mexicanos (United Mexican States). Mexico is a representative and democratic republic, composed of free states, united by a federal pact.

Therefore, the country is also known as Republica Mexicana (Republic of Mexico). The federal and state governments have their executive, legislative and judicial branches. The country is further divided into 32 states (see Figure 8). According to the 1917 constitution, the states are free and sovereign and have a constitution of their own (SRE, 2013) (Romero Ocampo, 2019, p. 18 - 19).

Figure 8: Mexico's Political Division

Source: Elaborated by author based on INEGI 2024

6.1.3 Population of Mexico

According to the 2020 census, Mexico's total population is 126'014,024 inhabitants (INEGI, 2021). Mexico's population is constantly growing and it is expected that by 2050 it will reach almost 150'000,000 inhabitants (Statista Research Department, 2023).

In 2022, approximately 81% of these inhabitants resided in urban areas (Grupo Banco Mundial, 2023). In response to this rapid urbanization, Mexican cities have devised diverse strategies to address the challenges related to urban growth, including urban mobility.

6.1.4 Mexico: an emerging country

The global market's expansion in the twentieth century led to the creation of the concept of emerging markets, which derived into the term emerging countries (Blázquez and Santiso, 2003). An emerging market economy is one that has not fully matured when compared with a developed one but has the potential to grow at an increased pace to become a developed market economy in the future years. Emerging market economies have greater risk because of the high returns and the higher risks associated. The challenges that investors face in emerging markets include the high risk, political instability, labor laws, social factors, policy amendments and implementations (Jangade, 2021, p. 386).

The E7, or Emerging 7, refers to the seven emerging economies in the world. These countries include China, India, Indonesia, Brazil, Turkey, South Korea, and Mexico (Vu, 2020). Since the twentieth century, Mexico has started to open its economy to the global arena, propelling its transition into an emerging country (Blázquez and Santiso, 2003).

6.1.5 Legal Actions towards Sustainability in Mexico

Though Mexico contributes only about 1.3% of GHG emissions, it is highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change (Gobierno de México, 2023, p. 1). Therefore, the country has undertaken challenges to address climate change. In October 2012 entered into effect the General Climate Change Law (LGCC) where the Mexican Government integrated the institutional framework stipulated by the legislation and the development of the policy instruments contemplated therein. The LGCC stipulates that in the national policy on mitigation the country should privilege actions with the greatest and least-cost potential for reducing emissions, and that generate co-benefits in health and well-being for the population (Mexico - Gobierno de la República, 2015, p. 6, 9).

In 2013 were installed the Inter-ministerial Commission on Climate Change, the Climate Change Council, and the new National Institute of Ecology and Climate Change. In that year it was also implemented the National Strategy on Climate Change. In 2014 the National System on Climate Change was installed. This System is integrated by Inter-ministerial Commission on Climate Change, the Climate Change Council, the National Institute of Ecology and Climate Change, subnational governments (states and municipalities) and the Mexican Congress (Ibidem.).

In matters of international relations, one of the powers and duties of the President of the Republic is to direct and conduct foreign policy, while the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Mexican Foreign Service are the entities responsible for the execution, direction and administration of foreign policy. The Mexican State has as a foreign policy principles enshrined in the Constitution, among others, the international cooperation for development, and the respect, protection and promotion of human rights (SRE, 2013). Therefore, in March 2015 Mexico was the first emerging country to submit its new climate action plan to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and in September 2016 Mexico signed the Paris Agreement (United Nations Treaty Collection, 2015) (United Nations Climate Change, 2015).

In 2015 Mexico presented its Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC) at COP21 (Mexico - Gobierno de la República, 2015, p. 6) and in 2020 updated the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) and presented them at Sharm el-Sheikh Climate Change Conference in Egypt (COP 27). These NDC contain an expanded ambition established at the COP 26 in Glasgow (Gobierno de México, 2022, p. 1, 11). This update considered the consequences of the SARS-CoV2 pandemic, where nations have been forced to rethink their development models. Mexico decided to adopt the United Nations 2030 Agenda and its 17 SDGs as the guiding axis of the inclusive development. In this context, Mexico, as a middle-income emerging country, committed to South-South and Triangular cooperations to support other countries in achieving more ambitious mitigation and adaptation goals. Mexico's focus will prioritize scientific and technological cooperation, the promotion of research, and capacity building, taking advantage of its strategic position to develop links with Latin America and the Caribbean (Gobierno de México. Secretaría de Medio Ambiente y Recursos Naturales, 2020, p. 9-10). In its last Position Paper towards the United Nations Climate Change Conference in Dubai (COP 28), Mexico states its targets included at the NDC with a focus on environmental justice, addressing areas such as transportation and energy (Gobierno de México, 2023, pp. 4–5).

6.1.6 Mobility policies and laws in Mexico

As mentioned in section 4.1.4, the transport sector in Mexico is one of the main sources of GHG and short-lived climate pollutants that have an impact in global warming and on the health of population. Therefore, the LGCC has prioritized their mitigation. The NDC contemplate an expanded ambition focused in transport sector, following the commitments established at COP 26. Mexico committed to accelerate efforts in Alliance with private sector and cities, for electric mobility and to consolidate the National Strategy for Electric Mobility in addition to promoting the transformation of public transport, which is the sector with greatest social impact. The goal is to reduce the carbon footprint of the vehicle fleet and encourage the transition to more efficient vehicles and the promotion of clean

transportation programs. The strategy for the transport sector highlights an improvement in linking urban planning with climate change criteria and the recovery of public space for pedestrians. The strategy considers a planning oriented to efficient public transport systems and alternative non-motorized transportation systems. These actions support compliance with the GHG target (Gobierno de México, 2022b, pp. 11–12).

Legislation about Mobility in Mexico

In 2020 the reform to the Constitutional Article 73° granted powers to the Congress of the Union to legislate on mobility and road safety. On 2021 the Senate approved the General Law of Mobility and Road Safety. In 2022, this Law became the only instrument at the federal level of mandatory observance for the federal entities in this matter (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 25).

The General Law of Mobility and Road Safety integrates the Active Mobility or non-motorized mobility concept as the displacement of people and goods that requires physical effort, using technical aids or non-motorized vehicles (Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión, 2023, p. 5). On the Article 6°, the Law establishes the Hierarchy of mobility:

“The planning, design and implementation of public policies, plans and programs in matters of mobility shall at all times favor the individual, groups in vulnerable situations and their needs, guaranteeing priority in the use and disposition of roads, in accordance with the following hierarchy of mobility:

I. Pedestrians, with an equitable and gender-differentiated approach; Persons with disabilities and limited mobility

II. Cyclists and users of non-motorized vehicles;

III. Users and providers of public passenger transportation services, with an equitable but differentiated approach;

IV. Persons providing transportation and distribution services of goods and merchandise;

V. Users of private motorized vehicles.”

(Idem., p. 11, Translated by author)

Biking in Mexico

Since 2013, Mexican cities have been progressing in bicycle mobility policies. There have been implemented projects such as the construction of bike lanes, bike-sharing systems, and the promotion of bicycle use through bicycle rides, campaigns, bicycle schools, recreational bike lanes. In 2019, the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States recognized the right of bicycles to be used as a means of mobility (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 25).

6.1.7 Smart City Initiatives in Mexico

In Mexico, certain cities have demonstrated a strong commitment to incorporating technology and possess the potential to evolve into Smart Cities. Such is the case of Mexico City, Guadalajara, and Puebla, among others (Goytia, 2022).

Smart City elements are emerging in Mexican cities, yet without explicit alignment with the intended Smart City objectives. In fact, Mexico does not have a Smart City as a whole, and the lack of a national strategy has affected the development of smart cities. By recognizing this non-intentional dispersion of efforts and addressing them, dimensions and stakeholders could work in alignment with a more cohesive and connected realization of the Smart City vision (Patiño Pastrana, 2015, pp. 1–5).

Example of implementation of Smart City elements: Mexico City

Security, monitoring, and access to the internet

An example of this implementation is the creation of the C5. The Command, Control, Computing, Communications and Citizen Contact Center of CDMX (C5) is the agency of the Government of Mexico City in charge of capturing comprehensive information for decision-making in public safety, medical emergencies, environment, civil protection, mobility, and community services in the capital of the country through video monitoring, telephone calls and intelligence applications, focused on improving the quality of life of the people of Mexico City (Gobierno de la Ciudad de México, 2024a). Mexico City has also implemented free Wi-Fi in public spaces as a right for all citizens, increasing the number of existing access points, locating them both in central areas and in the periphery to guarantee access for everyone (Gobierno de la Ciudad de México, 2024b).

Mobility

Mexico City has incorporated diverse platforms to promote sustainable mobility. An example is the Ecobici, a public shared-bike system that has integrated cycling into the urban mobility scenario. Ecobici provides a complementary app where users can see in real-time the availability of bikes and parking spots, verify the return of the bike, and inform in case of any problem. Parallel, Ecobici also collects data from its users and their routes (Gobierno de la Ciudad de México, 2023).

The Government of Mexico City has been one of the first Latin American cities to accept private car services such as Uber and DiDi. Mexico City's Government has worked to regulate these services to expand the transport market and provide an alternative to Taxi services. These services have increased the quality of life of citizens. Nevertheless, it is important to take into consideration aspects such as traffic congestion that these platforms still generate and the fact that these systems do not substitute low-cost mass public transport (García-Tejeda, 2016, pp. 40, 57-60).

In Mexico City, the Bus Rapid Transport BRT type Mass Transit System called Metrobus was included in other modes of transportation, where the technological factor was added as a basis to improve the efficiency of transportation in general. Evaluation of its efficiency should have a user centric approach when aiming for sustainable mobility. The technological change implied the shift from individual cards for each kind of transport in the city (metro, metrobus, etc.) to an intermodal card for all public transport. Metrobus also includes cameras for security and monitoring in real-time for any accidents or crimes. Users of Metrobus have recognized its connectivity with other Collective Transport Systems, nevertheless, they highlight that the connectivity diminishes when related with non-motorized transport, due to the lack of infrastructure.

Coordination

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs, through the Directorate of Liaison with Civil Society Organizations, in alliance with the UN-Habitat has conceived the Urban Laboratory: Interconnecting Smart Cities, with the objective of coordinating urban innovation efforts and making it the guiding axis of the Smart Urban Agenda in Mexico (Gobierno México, 2023).

6.2 Regional Context in Mexico: South-East Region

6.2.1 Regional Division of Mexico

Mexico can be divided according to certain regions: north, central, west central, and south-east (See Figure 9).

Figure 9: Mexico Regions

Source: Elaborated by author based on description of INEGI 2018, 2024

Figure 10: South-east Region

The southeastern region consists of 5 states: Chiapas, Tabasco, Campeche, Yucatan and Quintana Roo (See figure 10).

The total population of the 5 states was of 12.1 million in 2020. UN Habitat estimated that by 2030 the population would increase to 17.3 million, meaning an increase of 42.98% in 10 years (UN-Habitat, 2020a).

Source: Elaborated by author based on Google Maps, 2024

6.2.2 Regional Development in Mexico

Since the early eighties of the last century, Mexico's economic growth has developed unevenly by region and by social sector: while the entities of the North and Center exhibit moderate but acceptable growth rates, those of the South have suffered a real decrease (Secretaría de Gobernación, 2019).

The Special Economic Zones were one of the most important regional development projects, created in 2016 with the objective of closing the economic and social gap that exists between the south-southeast and the rest of the country. This should have been achieved through the promotion of investment, productivity, competitiveness, employment, and a better distribution of income among the population. With a coordinated effort between the three powers of the Union, the Federal Government, states and municipalities, the Inter-Secretarial Commission declared Special Economic Zones in Chiapas, Tabasco, Campeche, and Yucatán. All of which were declared by then President of Mexico Enrique Peña Nieto (Hernández, 2019). However, a few months after taking office as President, Andrés Manuel López Obrador (AMLO) eliminated the Special Economic Zones in 2019, under the argument that they had not been able to operate because they did not meet the legal requirements and that there were still no productive investments in them. The spokesperson for the Mexican Government stated that as part of AMLO Administration's economic plan, instead of continuing with the Special Economic Zones, priority will be given to regional development projects, such as the Mayan Train (going through the states of Chiapas, Tabasco, Campeche, Yucatán, and Quintana Roo), the Dos Bocas refinery (in Tabasco) and the Transisthmian Corridor. With these projects, the development is still focused in the south and south-eastern region, but through a different approach. They bring resources and infrastructure (Ibidem.).

Another central element of AMLO's campaign has been the Decentralization of the country. Therefore, since he was elected as President, decentralization has become one of his main goals. In the first campaign discourse, previous to his election, he stated that decentralization of the federal government is needed in order to have equal development among all the states of the republic. This highlights the aim for equal opportunities and access to resources throughout the country. Then, he talks about the current economic and social crisis in various regions of the country, marked by high levels of insecurity, unemployment, and violence. Therefore, it is understood that the decentralization plan has as motivation the desire to address these problems and improve the well-being of the population living across the country. The discourse also points out that the decentralization process will be carried out using voluntary agreements with government workers, including incentives such as access to education, affordable housing, and working opportunities. These with the objective to encourage workers to relocate, especially in the south and south-east regions (Gobierno de México, 2022a, pp. 62–68).

Due to this regional focus on the south-east development, federal resources have been allocated at the region to facilitate the construction of essential infrastructure projects and to host workers and investors related with the projects and those who need to move due to the decentralization process. As we move to the next chapter, the narrative will turn to the Yucatan State, exploring how these strategies impact at the local level in its mobility landscape and contribute to the broader goal of Mexico's pursuit of balanced development.

6.3 Local Context: Yucatan State and Merida City

As mentioned in section 4.2.3.1 Active Mobility Definition, among the factors that determine the Active Mobility behaviour are sociodemographic characteristics, sociopsychological, and sociogeographic factors. This section will discuss these elements on the local level.

6.3.1 Geographic Context

Merida is the capital City, located in the homonymous municipality, which is one of the 106 municipalities of the Yucatan State, situated in the Yucatan Peninsula (See Figure 11) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023a).

Figure 11: Merida City location

Source: Elaborated by author, 2023

Figure 12: Merida Geomorphology

Source: Geoportál de Mérida Yucatán, 2023

85.5% of Yucatan’s surface area has a warm sub-humid climate and the remaining 14.5% has a dry and semi-dry climate, which is located in the northern part of the state. The average annual temperature is 26°C, the average maximum temperature is around 36°C and occurs in the month of May; the average minimum temperature is 16°C and occurs in the month of January. The average annual precipitation in the state is 1,100 mm; rainfall is in the summer from June to October (INEGI, 2023). Merida is located within the Chixchulub crater. Its topography exhibits predominantly a flat terrain, with variations in the topography between the minimum altitude of 1 meter to the maximum altitude of 15 meters, with an average altitude of 9 meters. It consists mainly of level ground, minor elevations, gently sloping plains and dolines (see Figure 12) (Geoportál de Mérida Yucatán, 2023).

The conditions for non-motorized transport are ideal due to the lack of steep slopes. Nevertheless, weather plays an important role due to the high temperatures.

6.3.2 Sociodemographic Context of Merida

Merida City is the biggest and most populated city in the southeastern region of the country. In 2020, the population of Merida municipality was of 995,129 inhabitants, representing 42.8% of the 2'320,898 inhabitants of the Yucatan state (INEGI, 2023). Though under the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2022) (OCDE) standards Merida City might be considered a metropole or big city based on its population, in a country with cities such as Mexico City (9.2 million inhabitants) (INEGI, 2020), Merida is considered an intermediate city¹⁰ (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 158). As mentioned in the previous section, due to the decentralization effort carried out by the President of Mexico, the region is growing at a rapid pace (Gobierno de México, 2022a, pp. 62–68) and Merida is not an exception. This rapid growth and the new reception of investment and resources has shed light on the need for creating new and improving the existing infrastructure. Merida has grown almost 100 times in the last two centuries (Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, 2023). The municipality has an area of 858.41 km², equivalent to 2.18% of the area of the entire Yucatan state and 0.04% of the national territory (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2010). Today, the development of urban infrastructure and the diffuse expansion of the city has spread more rapidly, both in residential settlements for families with high purchasing power, as well as through the opening of wide and extensive roads, modern shopping malls, hotels and businesses of various types, including universities and private schools (Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, 2023). In 2015, Merida City started implementing digital tools that started the city's technological transformation, especially regarding Smart Mobility (Fernández, 2015).

6.3.3 Mobility in Merida

Figure 13: Road network and urbanized area of the municipality of Merida

Source: Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2020, p.14

Urban structure and morphology have direct implications on connectivity and accessibility. In particular, in Merida, the urban development model that has tended to expansion, fragmentation and discontinuity beyond the periphery, has serious implications on urban mobility. In addition, its communication with the rest of the urban layout is related to the road infrastructure and its carrying capacity. In this sense, there are urban and suburban areas with low connectivity in suburban housing developments and in the area surrounding the airport. The central area offers better accessibility conditions. The road network is mixed: to a large extent reticular, radial with respect to the center, connected by interior and peripheral circuits, and disjointed in suburban areas; however, it offers a regular degree of accessibility and allows for a hierarchical and differentiated network. The urban structure is polycentric, since the dynamics of urban development have led to the formation of sub-centers that bring together a good number of facilities and services that encourage travel to the city (Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2020, p. 14).

¹⁰ Intermediate cities are those with a population between 50 thousand and one million inhabitants (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 158).

6.3.3.1 Modes of Transport in Merida

The modes and forms of transport that people use to move around can be grouped as follows: pedestrian, non-motorized vehicular, public transport, and private vehicular (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2016, p. 18).

Pedestrian mode refers to the transfers on foot with or without load, as well as people with motor or sensory disabilities. In 2013, 9% of complete transfers were made on foot, meaning more than 129 thousand trips/person/day (Ibidem.).

Non-motorized vehicular mode refers to travel by bicycle, tricycle, skateboard and similar, and to elements and conditions that allow for the promotion of alternative means of transportation. Recently, special attention has been given to the use of bicycles as an indicator of sustainable urban mobility. For this reason, and as part of the public policy, projects that implement its use have been seen as strategic, both in the welfare and recreational spheres, to promote the city brand (Ibidem.).

Public transportation mode refers to urban buses (trucks), minibuses and collective cabs (combis), and taxis (combis). In 2013 in Mérida, 47% of all trips were made by public transport, which is the equivalent to more than 677 thousand trips/person/day (Ibidem.).

Motorized Vehicular refers to the private cars and motorcycles, as well as individualized service cabs. In 2013 in Mérida, 31% of all trips were made by these modes of modes of transportation, which represented 446 thousand trips/ person/day (Ibidem.).

6.3.3.2 Modal Split in Merida

Figure 14: Modal Split in Merida

According to the Origin Destination Survey of the Transportation Directorate of Yucatan State, the modal split of Merida City consisted of 46.9% for public transport, 31.5% for private transport (car), 4.3% for Taxi service, 2.6% for Mototaxi service, 9% for walking, 4.1% for bicycle, and 1.6% for other means of transport (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2016, p. 126).

Source: Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2020, p. 13

6.3.3.3 Challenges and Limitations in Urban Mobility in Merida

For pedestrian mobility, main limitations are found in the physical conditions of the public space (dimensions, levels, and textures of the sidewalks, obstacles due to furniture and infrastructure and infrastructure, design of crossings and ramps), and in local environmental conditions (climate). In addition to these difficulties in moving efficiently and comfortably, there are also safety risks, lack of universal accessibility, discontinuity of pedestrian infrastructure, and insufficient natural or artificial elements to mitigate the inclemency of the weather (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2016, p. 18).

For cycling infrastructure, limitations are related to problems that infrastructure presents in its use due to its design and level of connectivity, lack of signage, and being invaded by motorized vehicles, which results in a high rate of cycling accidents. To deal with these

problems, the city should increase the quantity and quality of road infrastructure to ensure that the city can provide more sustainable, efficient, economical, and adequate safety conditions. The city should also facilitate intermodality and interconnectivity in the road network for non-motorized vehicles (Ibidem.).

In terms of public transport, its operation had a negative impact on traffic conditions in the city, especially in the urban center since it is the convergence area for more than 90% of the routes. Statistics from 2013 show that 63% of users used up to 4 buses a day. The lack of transfer stations or interconnection points also played a role, and the urban center became a large transfer area with transfer stations. The local public transport system was overwhelmed by demand and was outdated; there was insufficient road infrastructure for non-motorized modes of transportation and pedestrian modes of transportation (Idem., pp. 19-20).

For the individualized use of private automobiles, the implications are related to an underutilization of the transfer possibilities of these vehicles, the increase in the demand for space in the city, and the congestion of urban traffic routes. Individualized use of private automobiles created the idea that it is a much more efficient option for commuting. However, the problems caused by having a large number of vehicles and a high percentage of car trips have an impact on the quality, efficiency, and safety of other modes of transport, and increase the environment pollution generated by urban mobility (Ibidem.).

6.3.3.4 Sustainable Mobility Goals in Merida

Merida City's Master plan for sustainable urban mobility highlights that in terms of mobility:

"[...] preference should be given to less polluting to less polluting modes of transport, those that require less urban space per passenger and those that move the most people and goods per unit of energy. In social cohesion criteria, we must favor those that favor those that promote contact among users, and between users and between users and public space and environment."

(Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2016, p. 16)

6.3.3.5 Funding mechanisms to implement mobility projects in Mexico

In order to implement or fund mobility projects, different resources can be used. At the federal level there are diverse funds and programs. Some examples are the Contribution Fund for the Strengthening of the Federal Entities, the Environmental Trusts (Climate Change Fund), and the Infrastructure Program of the Ministry of Agrarian and Territorial Urban Development. At the local level, there is the Metropolitan Fund. On the international level, there are different development agencies and banks capable of financing, at below-market interest rates, projects whose purpose is to promote the economic development of a given region or group of countries. Some examples of these institutions are the International Development Bank, The Development Bank of Latin America, and the German Association for Technical Cooperation. Another type of financial resources that can be accessed is private resources. These mechanisms can generally be beneficial for the maintenance and operation of programs such as public bicycle, intermodal stations, bicycle parking or other systems. Also, in the installation of infrastructure through schemes that are agreed with the competent authorities in the matter. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) represent a good tool to maintain the pace of investment in infrastructure and development projects, both essential to improve the quality of life of citizens. The advantages of PPPs are clear: they represent additional funds for governments, beyond public resources, to invest in development projects (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2016, pp. 37–38).

6.3.4 Active Mobility in Merida

6.3.4.1 Promotion of Active Mobility in Merida

Mérida has several ambitious strategies to promote Active Mobility. In 2016, the government of the State of Yucatán published a non-motorized mobility plan for the metropolitan area of Mérida, thus initiating a process of design process of the cycling infrastructure network, with the participation of experts and citizens. Two years later, in 2018, the Institute for Mobility and Urban-Territorial Development was created, which is in charge of designing, implementing, and evaluating public policies in urban development, mobility, and cultural heritage conservation. The creation of IMDUT signified an important change in the governance and integral planning of mobility in the state. In 2019, the Integral Plan for Sustainable Urban Mobility (PIMUS) 2040, for Mérida, was published. This provides authorities with regulatory, technical and financial tools for the implementation of projects. In 2021, the Bases and Strategies to strengthen the use of bicycles for sustainable mobility in the State of Yucatan were also published, which foresees the implementation of a network of bicycle lanes. This set of plans makes it possible to frame the promotion of Active Mobility in public mobility policies, such as in street restructuring projects (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 174).

6.3.4.2 Active Mobility projects in Merida

Complete Street Project: Paseo Montejo

Complete Streets are roadways designed and operated to provide safety, accessibility, and healthy travel for all street users, regardless of age, gender, abilities, or preferred mode of transportation. This is achieved through road redistribution interventions to ensure proper street operation (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 33).

Figure 15: Paseo de Montejo Avenue

Source: Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 170.

In Merida City, the Intervention took place in Paseo de Montejo Avenue (see figure 15), one of the main arteries of the city and an important tourist corridor with high pedestrian traffic. Paseo Montejo lacked quality cycling and pedestrian infrastructure. Therefore in 2021 The Complete Street Project was implemented (Idem., p. 173). 1.6 km in length were intervened. The intervention Included construction of 740.50 m² of sidewalks and ramps, rehabilitation of 741.25 m² of sidewalks and 1,743.07 m of sidewalk lining (Idem., p. 171).

In terms of road redistribution, the project involved narrowing vehicle lanes from 3.60 m to 3.00 m. This included the implementation of a 1.5 m-wide cycle lane with buoys, rehabilitation of sidewalks, and reorganization of on-street parking to serve as a confining element for the cycle lane (see figure 16). Additionally, intersections were redesigned to

enhance pedestrian and cyclist safety. Regarding urban furniture and devices, the project included the installation of vertical signage indicating cyclist crossings and the start and end of the cycle lane, as well as horizontal markings such as crosswalks for pedestrians and cyclists, directional indicators for vehicles, pictograms, etc. A total of 3,469 pedestrian traffic lights and 853 assistance lights were placed. Additionally, trash bins and "sillas confidentes" (typical Yucatan benches for two people) were installed, as well as water fountains.

Furthermore, 127 short-stay bike racks were set up to encourage cycling. Finally, Planters with ornamental plants and LED streetlights were installed (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 171).

Figure 16: Comparison of cross sections of Paseo Montejo

Source: Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 172.

In Mérida, citizen coordination appeared in opposition to the redesign project. However, the authorities made a notable effort to communicate about the project and the need to improve road coexistence for all modes of transportation. In addition, during the 2021 election campaign, several candidates showed their support for the project and the extension of the cycling infrastructure network at public events. At the same time, civil society organizations focused on demanding improved mobility conditions for people on bicycles were also formed (Ibidem.).

Investment

Merida had the average amount of investment allocated from the Federal Expenditure Budget for bicycle mobility. With this investment, projects such as the construction of bicycle lanes and cycling infrastructure plans were implemented (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 39).

Mérida also granted financing credits to state workers affiliated to the Instituto de Seguridad Social de los Trabajadores del Estado de Yucatán for the purchase of bicycles, and also provided tax benefits to companies, businesses and stores to acquire bicycles for their workers (Idem., p. 42).

Finally, Merida implemented the bicycle credit program "Impulso a la movilidad sostenible", which covers 50% of the purchase of a bicycle and allows the rest to be paid in installments (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 177).

Intermodality: Bicycle integration

The integration of bicycles into the public transport network makes it possible to generate intermodal trips in the city. In the city of Merida, public transport units are equipped with racks (see Figure 17) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023).

Figure 17: Bicycle racks in public transport in Merida

Source: Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023.

Bicycle rental service

Figure 18: En Bici campaign

Source: Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023

Translation: We extend the date! Free rides by registering the code ENBICI24. Valid until February 29, 2024. Enjoy En bici for free until February 29.

The "En Bici" program is an initiative of the Mérida City Hall. It was inaugurated in May 2023. It is a transport system that provides a bicycle rental service similar to EcoBici in Mexico City. The service has an app through which you can reserve and return a bicycle, look for free parking spots, availability of bikes, and register the end of the trip (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023). Initially, the project has 300 bicycles and 100 bike stations throughout the city. During the implementation phase, the service was free for the first three months (Santiago, 2023). Nevertheless, the Ayuntamiento de Mérida (2023) website has continued to offer free service until February 2024 (see Figure 18).

Bicycle routes

Merida municipality has instituted nine-day cycling routes, strategically closing streets on Sundays to facilitate and promote active mobility within the city. These routes incorporate amenities such as bike renting, toilets, and repair stations. Additionally, once per month a night route is organized at Paseo de Montejo avenue, that is closed temporarily to enhance accessibility and safety of nighttime cycling for the community. The routes are shared digitally through the government website (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024a).

Additional measures

Some additional measures to promote bicycle use include the installation of a citizen's council for the promotion of bicycle use in the metropolitan area of Merida, which has focused on generating data on cycling infrastructure. These measures also comprise the adoption of bases and strategies defined in the sustainable mobility plans for the expansion of the cycling network and the promotion of cycling (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 177).

Merida Evaluation of Active Mobility

At the Cyclocities Ranking 2021, diverse elements were evaluated. The following categories were taken into consideration for the evaluation: Environment, Institutional capacity, Education and promotion, Intermodality, Investment, Monitoring and evaluation, Other incentives, Urban planning, Bicycle mobility network, Regulation, Road Safety. These categories were based on indicators such as how Active Mobility is linked to goals to reduce the GHG and its monitoring system, the existence of an area in charge of sustainable urban mobility policies, interinstitutional and regional coordination to implement those policies and projects, strategies and actions from both government and civil society to inform and raise awareness among citizens, the integration of bicycles as part of the public transport system, local or federal government investment for its planning and implementation, bicycle use monitoring through data collection, the grant of incentives, inclusion of bicycle mobility in urban planning instruments and programs, if the existing infrastructure is comfortable, direct, coherent and safe, as well as the amount of deaths and accidents, amongst others (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, pp. 21-24).

Merida city got the following punctuation:

Table 3: Distribution of points in 2021 by evaluation axis of Mérida, Yucatán

		Environment	Institutional capacity	Education and promotion	Intermodality	Investment	Monitoring and evaluation	Other incentives	Urban planning	Bicycle mobility Network	Regulation	Road Safety
Ciudad	Puntos totales											
Mérida	47.00	2	5	4	2	2	6	1.5	8	7	8.5	1.0
	%	50	63	44	17	20	55	75	89	54	65	11

Source: Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 53. Translated by author.

In terms of intermodality, Merida stood out thanks to the bicycle racks integrated into the units. Regarding investment, the city also complied with the average investment of the Federal Expenditure Budget in bicycle mobility. Regarding modal split and gender, Mérida was also recognized because the percentage of women who use bicycles as a means of transportation is higher than the national average of 20%. In terms of incentives, Merida granted financing credits to state workers affiliated to the Institute of Social Security for the Workers of the State of Yucatan for the purchase of bicycles. It also provided tax benefits to companies, businesses, and stores to purchase bicycles for their workers. In terms of growth in cycling infrastructure, the COVID-19 pandemic prompted the implementation of bike lanes for bicycle mobility in Merida, which then implemented pop-up bike lanes as a solution to pandemic mobility and converted them into infrastructure. Similarly, during 2021, cycling-inclusive projects were implemented, such as the Joint Program to Improve Mobility in Merida (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, pp. 12, 41, 42, 44).

Merida has thrived in the local context by being the most representative city for the ranking and achieving the highest number of points in the region (see Table 3). Nevertheless, there is still potential to enhance these areas, and the Smart City approach could facilitate that improvement, especially in the categories with the lowest amount of points, such as Intermodality, Investment, road safety, and Education and promotion.

6.3.5 Smart City Approaches in Merida

As mentioned in the section 7.1.7, certain Mexican cities have demonstrated a strong commitment to incorporating technology and possess the potential to evolve into Smart Cities (Goytia, 2022), though they do not have an explicit alignment with the intended Smart City objectives (Patiño Pastrana, 2015, pp. 1–5). Such is the case of Merida. The following sub-sections will provide some of the Smart City approaches present in Merida, as well as international cooperation involved.

6.3.5.1 Monitoring systems in Merida

This chapter will provide insights on Smart City approaches and technologies implemented in Merida. Specifically, the monitoring systems currently implemented to track and detect different factors that improve the quality of life of citizens in terms of security and air quality.

Security – C5i

Center for Control, Command, Communications, Computing, Coordination and Intelligence, also known as C5i, is a specialized building designed to coordinate and help officers in the event of a crime, allowing them to have a fast response to pursue and capture the criminals, making safer the life of citizens. This place gathers the organizational techniques and tactics used by the Police Department. Nowadays, C5i integrate technologies such as networks of cameras, panic alarms, videowalls, phone lines, and even Artificial Intelligence that helps to detect and flag, in real-time, crimes being committed. This facilitates the Police Departments response to crimes (Algorithmic Objective Corp., 2023).

In Yucatan state, due to the growth of Merida City and the state in general, the facilities of the Police Monitoring and Intelligence unit required to expand their capacity. Therefore the state government invested more than 110 million Mexican pesos to build the new C5i facilities (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2021a). In 2022, the Governor of Yucatan state inaugurated the C5i, from where the entire video surveillance system will be controlled. The system will increase from 2,248 cameras to 6,775 and from 100 road arches to 219, among other actions. The goal is better coordination and prompt response of the state police (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2022).

Additionally, the Yucatan Seguro state program incorporates the installation of intelligent traffic lights, posts with panic buttons, new video surveillance cameras and road arches¹¹ (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2021a).

Air Quality

In 2012, the Air Quality Monitoring System (SMCA YUCATAN) was implemented by the Secretariat of Sustainable Development of Yucatan State. The system consists of a Continuous Monitoring Station that contains automatic analyzers, monitors and/or meteorological sensors, among others, destined to measure the concentrations of one or more air pollutants and some meteorological parameters. The purpose is to evaluate the quality of the air in a determined area. The station provides real-time information and allows the registration of the concentrations of pollutants in the air automatically and continuously. These pollutants are particulate matter less than or equal to 2.5 micrometers (PM2.5), ozone (O3), sulfur dioxide (SO2), nitrogen dioxide (NO2) and carbon monoxide (CO). In 2016, the SMCA YUCATAN was connected to the National Air Quality Information System which generates real-time information from monitoring stations by state, thus

¹¹ The road arches are metallic structures that are installed in strategic points of the main avenues, roads or highways as support to the C5i of the Government offices in charge of Public Security. Technology equipments could include video surveillance cameras, license plate recognition detection cameras, message panels, RDFI cards, dispatch and emergency call answering systems, alarm buttons, large format screens , etc. (Realcom Antenas y Torres, 2024).

creating a nationwide monitoring network (Secretaría de Desarrollo Sustentable del Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2018) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024b).

6.3.5.2 Mobility of Merida

Bike sharing systems

As mentioned in the section 6.3.4.2, the "En Bici" program is not only relevant in terms of mobility, but also from a Smart City approach. This bike sharing system initiative takes advantage of technology and promotes sustainable and efficient movement. The app to manage the system allows to reserve and return a bicycle, look for free parking spots, availability of bikes, and register the end of the trip. With an initial fleet of 300 bicycles and 100 bike stations spread throughout the city (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023), this is a good example of the implementation of a Smart City approach in Merida.

Public Transport

On 2021, Yucatán State inaugurated an Integrated Transportation System (SIT, standing for Sistema Integral de Transporte) called Metropolitan System of Friendly and Sustainable Mobility, also known as Va y Ven (in Spanish: goes and comes) (Farfán, 2021). This project offers urban buses services (see Figure 17) in eight routes throughout the metropolitan area of Merida (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024f). Va y Ven has a mobile application through which users can consult schedules, routes and stops. Buses and travel time information is updated in real time, allowing passengers to choose the route that suits them best (Banco Nacional de Obras y Servicios Públicos, S.N.C., 2023). Intelligent Payment is made through a rechargeable smart card with geolocation that charges according to the distance traveled, and it offers free transfers (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024d).

MaaS and MoD

Actually, Merida has different private driving services (MaaS and MOD) platforms, such as Uber and DiDi. Uber was the pioneer platform to arrive in 2016. Though initially the platform encounter different challenges with the so-called "Ley Anti-Uber" (Law Anti-Uber), on 2017 the Transportation Law of Yucatan was officially enacted (Rodríguez, 2017). DiDi arrived in 2017, and in 2019 they opened a new Drivers Club in Merida, with the objective to bring support services to drivers affiliated to the platform, where they get clarifications regarding taxes payment, the use of the application and earning scheme, among others (DiDi, 2019).

Smart Traffic Lights

In 2021, through the state government, started the installation of 2,646 smart traffic lights for pedestrians. These traffic lights will be monitored and controlled at the C5i. In total, 307 crossings will be intervened through 321 controllers and 212 radars. The goal is to achieve the smart control of (adaptive) traffic, a central system of traffic lights that prioritizes emergency vehicles as well as optimizing public transport and improving the overall security of pedestrians and cyclists. The allocated budget amounts to 441 million Mexican pesos (Gobierno de Yucatán, 2021).

6.3.5.3 International Cooperation in Smart Infrastructure Development

Technical Assistance Grant

In April 2021 President Biden launched the United States Trade and Development Agency (USTDA)'s Global Partnership for Climate-Smart Infrastructure to connect U.S. industry to major clean energy and transportation infrastructure projects in emerging economies (U.S. Trade and Development Agency, 2021). In 2022, the USTDA awarded a technical assistance grant to Yucatan State through the Institute of Mobility and Territorial Urban Development to modernize the public transportation system in Mérida. Assistance will advance the deployment of intelligent transportation system (ITS) technologies and electric mobility solutions across the city. The goal is to help achieve carbon-free transportation goals (U.S. Trade and Development Agency, 2022). The Intelligent Transportation System

modernization project will update the bus control and monitoring center and advance the transition to electric buses for Mérida's public transportation fleet. The impact of the project seeks to improve public transportation in Mérida by enhancing overall system performance, bus control and monitoring operations and safety (Iteris, Inc., 2023).

Smart City Congress

The Smart City Expo World Congress is an international reference event for cities all around the globe. It has been held in Barcelona since 2011 with the goal to empower cities and collectivize urban innovations worldwide by promoting social innovation and identifying opportunities for collaboration. The Latin American branch of the Congress (Smart City Expo Latam Congress – SCELIC) has taken place in Merida since 2019 (SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V, 2023), integrating Merida in the Global Network of Smart Cities.

SCELIC24 aims to share the effort, between public and private actors to implement viable actions that guarantee real impacts that contribute to generate more sustainable, technological and inclusive societies. The SCELIC24 is the meeting point for influential leaders implementing Smart City approaches in Latin America (Ibidem.). At the announcement of the SCELIC24, Yucatan State Governor expressed that the Congress would take place once more in Merida because Yucatan and Merida aim to become the structural bridge between Europe and Latin America, connecting all the transformative actors in benefit of the territory and its citizens (Agencia EFE, 2023).

7 Enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City Approach in Merida

As seen in the previous section, Merida City has implemented both Smart City and Active Mobility approaches. In some projects, both concepts merge and complement each other. However, it is important to analyze what conditions have been presented to allow this synergy.

In terms of Active Mobility, the geography of the City plays an important role. Most of the Yucatan Peninsula is flat land. Regarding Merida City, there are no outside rivers in the area, and the most outstanding geographic feature could be the cenotes¹², though they run underground. Therefore, since there are no geographic obstacles, bicycle, scooter, motorcycle and walking commuting are easy and comfortable. This makes an ideal setting for Active Mobility (Cisneros, 2024).

In terms of climate conditions, Lee and Pojani (2019) highlight that local climate and weather conditions are less inhibiting for travellers used to their respective climates. Therefore, infrastructure, such as bike lanes, bike-sharing schemes, and bike parking and charging stations, is a major factor when promoting Active Mobility. Cities in hot climates, such as Singapore, Mexico City, San Francisco or Sevilla have implemented strategies that include the positioning of new segregated bike lanes along main avenues with existing cover, increasing the green cover, implementing innovative cooling surfaces (such as materials that reflect, cool, and/or minimize the heat radiating from surfaces), and promoting e-bikes use through financial incentives and expansion of charging stations and bike parking facilities (Merforth, 2023). Merida has significantly improved its Active Mobility infrastructure, introducing safe bike lanes parallel to green-covered streets, such is the case of the expansion of 71.7 km for new bike lanes throughout the whole city, including Paseo de Montejo avenue (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024e). Merida municipality has instituted nine-day cycling routes, strategically closing streets on Sundays to facilitate and promote active mobility within the city. These routes incorporate amenities such as bike renting, toilets, and repair stations. Additionally, once per month a night route is organized at Paseo de Montejo avenue, that is closed temporarily to enhance accessibility and safety of nighttime cycling for the community (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024a).

In terms of Smart City, Merida was enrolled in the Smart City network promoted through Smart City Expo World Congress. This Congress has exported the European scheme to Asia and Latin America. In Latin America the venue of the Smart City Expo Latam Congress (SCELC) has taken place in Merida during the last 3 years (SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V, 2023). This has allowed to put Merida in actions to digitize the city and its mobility. Cisneros (2024) highlights efficiency, sustainability and cooperation when talking about digitalization in Merida. He explained that through the georeferenced payment of the Metropolitan System of Friendly and Sustainable Mobility (Va y Ven) card, the payment of the bus trips is based in the distance, and also has a differentiated social rate of pay, which makes it an intelligent payment system. Cisneros also underlined the importance of the construction of 36 km of bicycle lanes that promote sustainable mobility through bicycles and scooters, with an emphasis in digital mobility. Finally, he pointed the importance of exchange platforms, such as the SCELC, where good practices are presented and awarded, and cities such as Merida can inspire from these models. For example, the installation of cameras to increase security and security perception.

Finally, regarding society, Cisneros (Ibidem.) expressed that the digitization platforms have been well accepted by society in Merida because they improve people's quality of life. He also noted that Merida has cultural strength and power based on its solid and rooted

¹² Cenotes are sinkholes, i.e. topographic depression formed when underlying limestone bedrock is dissolved by groundwater (Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc., 2024).

Mayan¹³ culture. Therefore, when digitalized networks, such as 5G arrive, the strong technological change is accepted by the society, because the society itself is prepared to withstand the impact of that technological force. This provides a very strong cultural support, that helps the assimilation of new technologies without undermining its identity or culture due to its solidity and lack of vulnerability, what brings a great competitive advantage.

However, Arndt (2024) highlights that *smart* approaches should be also understood as user-friendly and accessible for everyone. This includes, for instance, ensuring that sharing systems' applications are easy to use and operate through diverse models to accommodate different user preferences and needs. This promotes an efficient and pleasant experience for the final users.

Once the above point has been established, this section will analyze how Smart City approach has enhanced Active Mobility in Merida as well as the areas of opportunity.

7.1 Existing enhancement of Active Mobility with Smart City approach in Merida

7.1.1 Indirect enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City approach

Security and Air Quality

Some projects with a Smart City approach implemented in Merida impact in an indirect way on Active Mobility. Such is the case of the C5i and the air quality monitoring system.

As mentioned in section 3.2.4.2, in emerging countries, urban safety plays a greater role. It is common that in Latin America, Smart City projects are implemented within the framework of international cooperation networks with the private sector, research institutes and universities (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 19–20). Due to unstable political situation and high crime rates, some Latin American cities have implemented digital systems that intend for control and public surveillance (Ruiz and Tigre, 2014, p. 85-95) (Singer, 2012), as well as real-time monitor of meteorological, crime, traffic and emergency data, collected live from cam feeds from all over the city (Prefeitura do Rio de Janeiro, 2012, pp. 64–67).

Merida has positioned itself as the safest city in the country, with the lowest crime rate in Mexico, 9 times lower than the national average. Part of this achievement is attributed to the installation of the C5i and the implementation of the Yucatan Seguro state program (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023b). The incorporation of intelligent traffic lights, posts with panic buttons, new surveillance cameras and road arches (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2021a) has improved the safety perception and has become an incentive for the population to increase active mobility activity. Parallel, these devices can monitor diverse indicators (such as weather, air quality, traffic, etc.) that can be shared with the citizens and allows them to choose the best or more convenient routes. The system also allows to spot accidents or crimes in real-time and connect with emergency services.

Through monitoring systems and intelligent technologies based on the Smart City approach, inhabitants of Merida get incentivized to use the public space in a city with a positive safety perception. They also get the opportunity to choose the best and/or more efficient route and mean of transport to reach their destinations.

Cooperation and Education

The presence of The Smart City Expo Latam Congress – SCELIC) in Merida since 2019 can provide diverse opportunities to enhance Active Mobility through the Smart City approach.

¹³ The Maya of the Yucatan Peninsula are the second largest Mesoamerican people in Mexico in terms of numbers and are the heirs of what is considered the most dazzling civilization of pre-Columbian America. The Mayas constitute today one of the indigenous nuclei of greater quantitative and qualitative weight of Indigenous Mexico (Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, 2015).

First, by integrating Merida in the Global Network of Smart Cities and also by being the host city, it attracts new talents and ideas each year. Merida can benefit from the exchange of knowledge and best practices presented at the Congress, as well as to acquire new vision on how Smart City approaches can enhance active mobility and what new technologies are being used to do so. It also brings opportunities for collaboration at a national and international level, with both public and private actors that can help implement viable actions that guarantee real impacts that contribute to generate more sustainable, technological, and inclusive societies (SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V., 2023). It also provides, at a government level, the possibility to apply for funds and to bridge diverse actors in benefit of the territory, for example, Europe and Latin America (Agencia EFE, 2023).

These Forums based on Smart City approach promote interaction and exchange to acquire new visions for the implementation of Active Mobility to acquire the development of sustainable and efficient cities.

7.1.2 Direct enhancement of Active Mobility through Smart City approach

Once analyzed some Smart City projects that have an indirect effect in Active Mobility, this section will analyze those that have a direct impact in Active Mobility.

As mentioned in section 4.2.3, Active Mobility, is the use of non-motorized mobility (i.e. walking and cycling) for transport, either solely or in combination with public transport (Gerike *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, bicycle sharing systems and public transport are important components when talking about Active Mobility.

MaaS and Bicycle shared system

As mentioned in section 4.2.2.2 and 4.2.2.3, Smart Mobility solutions are gaining prominence in applications such as the use of new technologies for transport and the optimization of the existing ones (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, p. 36). In cities, such as Merida, mobility services provided to users on smartphones have started to transition towards shared vehicle usage rather than the traditional vehicle ownership (Mohieldin and Vandycke, 2017). It is under this context that the trend Mobility as a Service (MaaS) develops, based on the idea that mobility is a service that is rented and paid for (Sengupta, 2022).

The "En Bici" program inaugurated in 2023 in Merida, is the first digital bicycle rental system in Yucatan. The system works with an app through which you can reserve and return a bicycle, look for free parking spots, availability of bikes, and register the end of the trip (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023). Initially, the projects has 300 bicycles and 100 bike stations throughout the city (Santiago, 2023).

"En Bici" project takes advantage of the Smart City approach to promote Active mobility, especially cycling. By using MaaS and Bicycle shared systems based on an application that integrates digital technologies and geoinformation systems to consult the bikes availability and parking spots, active mobility is enhanced.

Public Transport

The implementation in 2021 of the Metropolitan System of Friendly and Sustainable Mobility, also known as Va y Ven (Farfán, 2021) has been a milestone in digitalization and Integrated Transportation System in Merida. First, it has increased and improved the exiting routes throughout the metropolitan area of Merida (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024f). Secondly, Va y Ven has improved non-motorized mobility (especially walking and cycling) by encouraging people to use these modes of transport. For example, as shown in section 6.3.3 in Figure 17, buses have integrated bicycle racks, promoting intermodal trips in the city. Thirdly, it has implemented a mobile application where users can consult schedules, routes and stops, as well as monitor buses and travel time information in real time (Banco Nacional de Obras y Servicios Públicos, S.N.C., 2023). Lastly, the payment made through a rechargeable smart card that contains geolocation is also a very innovative practice in the

region (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024d). Additionally, Va y Ven is implementing a 100% electric route, being the first one in the southeast. Parallel, there are under planning the Modal Transfer Centers, where modes of transport can interconnect by prioritizing the use of public transport, user transfers, and the development of infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024c).

Therefore, the Va y Ven project has enhanced Active Mobility through Smart City approaches that improve and promote non-motorized mobility, integrate these forms with public transport, provide real-time information through digitalization and monitoring, and make more efficient the payment experience through the innovative payment system.

7.2 Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Merida: promotion of walking and cycling

This section explains how Smart City technologies improve cycling and pedestrian infrastructure in Merida, and how these encourage walking as a mode of transport as well as urban safety.

Table 4 shows the Active Mobility and Smart City projects implemented in Merida, and how they interconnect regarding their goals and objectives.

Table 4: Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Merida

Active Mobility			Smart City
Complete Street Project: Paseo de Montejo	Complete Street Project	←	C5i - Security
Investment allocated from the Federal Expenditure Budget for bicycle mobility		→	Air Quality Monitoring System
Financing credits to state workers for the purchase of bicycles	Investment	→	En Bici transport system that provides a bicycle rental service through an app where you can reserve and return a bicycle, look for free parking spots, availability of bikes, and register the end of the trip
Tax benefits to companies, businesses and stores to acquire bikes for their workers		→	Integrated Transportation System: Metropolitan System of Friendly and Sustainable Mobility, also known as Va y Ven
Bike credit program "Impulso a la movilidad sostenible" that covers 50% of the purchase of a bike and allows to be paid in installments		→	MaaS & MOD
Uber, Didi, En Bici		→	
Bike integration through racks in public transport units, Bikes parking	Intermodality	→	Investment
USTDA awarded a technical assistance grant to Yucatan State through the Institute of Mobility and Territorial Urban Development to modernize the public transportation system in Mérida.		→	International cooperation & Education
En Bici transport system that provides a bicycle rental service through an app.	Bike rental service	→	Infrastructure
Creation of citizen council for promotion of bike use	Citizen participation	→	Smart traffic lights for pedestrians controlled and monitored through C5i
Cicloranking	Monitoring and Evaluation	→	
Bicycle routes	Bike Routes	→	

Source: Elaborated by author, 2024

For example, the Active Mobility project Complete Street: Paseo de Montejo has a direct relation with the monitoring systems of C5i and Air Quality Monitoring System to promote urban safety for cyclists and pedestrians. It also connects indirectly with the MaaS and MoD sharing systems “En Bici”, for stations are located at the Paseo de Montejo street and also the bike lanes can be used by the shared bikes, promoting cycling. The Improvement of sidewalks and ramps also enhances walking. The connection with the Smart traffic lights aims to improve overall security of pedestrians and cyclists.

In terms of Active Mobility investment, the relation goes directly with investment in terms of Smart City, such as the USTDA technical assistance grant, as well as to the improvement of Public Transport (Integrated Transportation System Va y Ven), as well as with the International Cooperation, where through forums such as the SCELIC, it is possible to learn from best practices globally and also create a network that could include diverse actors and

funding mechanisms. This investment translates in an improvement of infrastructure, which means a direct encouragement to the use of active modes such as walking or cycling.

Regarding intermodality, the main connections are related with Monitoring systems that promote urban safety and that track accidents or crimes (C5i), as well as with public transport systems (Va y Ven) that promote different transport means to reach the destination, while promoting walking and cycling. Finally, investment also plays a role in this regard, for the improvement and modernization of the transport units requires resources such as the USTDA technical grant.

The Bike rental service En Bici is both an active mode and a Smart City component, that provides mobility as a service (MaaS). Through the use of the app to find, book and return a bike, this system promotes cycling and, indirectly, walking.

The citizen participation plays a very important role when promoting Active Modes through Smart City approach, especially when detecting areas of improvement and proposing the implementation of innovative projects that enhance walking and cycling, such as the MaaS En Bici bike sharing program, as well as the pressure to improve public transport, such as the Va y Ven system. The creation of the citizen council for promotion of bike use in Merida is an example.

Ranking and evaluation projects also play an important role when monitoring status, quality, and opportunities for Active Mobility approaches. In the case of the Cycloranking, among the aspects that were evaluated, were those related with Smart City approaches. For example, the implementation of MaaS bike system En Bici, and the conditions of public transport (such as Va y Ven). It also included investment on the national level. It is under these considerations that improvements can be detected and that assets can be recognized to continue providing people the quality infrastructure that will encourage the population to walk and cycle more.

Finally, joint effort between government and community to develop the Cycling routes plays an important role when promoting walking and cycling. By closing the streets once per week and once per month during the night, society integration is achieved by allowing families and citizens to gather and walk or cycle in a safe car-free space. The routes and days are shared digitally through the government website and social networks. These efforts are directly linked with the bike sharing system “En Bici” for the shared bikes can be used at the cycling routes. And also is related with the education and international cooperation network, where it can be shared as a best practice and acquire different insights and smart components present in other cycling routes globally.

Through these actions, walking and cycling are encouraged and linked to Smart City technologies and approaches, by enhancing urban safety.

7.2.1 Areas of opportunity

Merida City has already implemented Smart City approaches in benefit of its mobility, both active and motorized. Nevertheless, there is still opportunity to grow and improve in certain areas. And is important to create a strategy to take advantage of the Smart City approach benefits.

In general terms, as mentioned in chapter 6.1.7, certain Mexican cities have demonstrated a strong commitment to incorporating technology and possess the potential to evolve into Smart Cities (Goytia, 2022). However, the Smart City elements are emerging without explicit alignment with the intended Smart City objectives. As mentioned before, Mexico does not have a Smart City as a whole, and the lack of a national strategy has affected the development of smart cities (Patiño Pastrana, 2015, pp. 1–5). Though Merida is part of the global network of Smart Cities due to its participation at the Smart City Expo Latam Congress – (SCELC) (SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V, 2023), there is still an opportunity to create a local or regional strategy and vision to benefit from the Smart City approach, such as the integration to the Smart Urban Agenda in Mexico, that guarantees coordinating urban innovation efforts (Gobierno México, 2023).

In the future, when implementing projects such as the Complete Street Paseo de Montejo, Smart City technologies (such as WiFi, panic buttons, smart traffic lights, monitoring tools, etc.) could be embedded in the urban furniture and conceptualized from the planning and urban design stages to promote road safety.

Another area of opportunity is related with taking advantage of nature and its benefits. For example, strong winds in the region can be used to generate wind power and electricity using wind turbines. Other sustainable sources of energy used in the region include photovoltaic energy produced through solar energy. These two sustainable sources of energy can provide electricity for the Smart City systems implemented (Cisneros, 2024).

Another advantage is that most of the municipalities and cities in Yucatan state have electrical network. In the future, a network will be implemented. Through the electric column, internet signal transmitters could be installed, guaranteeing internet access not only for citizens, but also for industry, Closed-circuit television (cctv), transportation, alerts, etc. (Ibidem.).

Geography also plays an important role when analysing the areas of opportunity of Merida City. Due to its flat surface, WiFi and internet signals can go through without obstacles that interfere such as mountains or volcanos (Ibidem.).

7.2.2 Resilience and Adaptability

Merida is a city that has learned from its challenges and worked to tackle them. Such is the case of the Cyclicities Ranking 2021, where the city got the lower amount of points in terms of investment, intermodality and road safety (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, pp. 21-24). However, since then, several projects with a Smart City approach have been developed to face these shortcomings. For example, the Va y Ven project solves some of these challenges related with investment and intermodality. In 2021 the USTDA awarded a technical assistance grant to Yucatan State through the Institute of Mobility and Territorial Urban Development to modernize the public transportation system in Mérida, implemented in the Va y Ven project (U.S. Trade and Development Agency, 2022). The same Va y Ven system also includes bicycle racks that promote intermodal trips in the city (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023). Finally, regarding road safety diverse actions have taken place, including the installation of the C5i, the implementation of smart street lighting and complete street projects such as Paseo de Montejo.

7.2.3 Effect of Smart City promotion of Active Modes in Merida

The promotion of Active Mobility with a Smart City approach has different effects, including a positive influence in urban mobility, public health, environmental sustainability, and overall quality of life (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p.1,2). In the context of Merida, the effect is directly related with improved physical infrastructure (i.e., improvement and increment of new bike lanes, bikes parking, increase of green coverage), enhanced safety through monitoring systems and incorporation of technologies (such as intelligent traffic lights and C5i system), and digitalization of Smart Mobility solutions (such as the implementation of Va y Ven card system to pay according to the distance traveled) (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 171) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024d). It also implies the encouragement of sustainable practices, such as the promotion of public transport (i.e., Va y Ven project) and promotion of Active Modes such as biking (i.e. bikes racks in buses or En Bici bike sharing systems) to reduce carbon footprint associated with transportation (Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024f). Indirectly, it also promotes Public Health by encouraging physical activity and a healthier lifestyle (Mela and Girardi, 2022, p.1,2). Finally, in the specific case of Merida, its cultural strength rooted in the Mayan culture allows society to embrace technological changes without compromising its identity (Cisneros, 2024).

8 Analysis and Transferability

As mentioned in the section 4.2.2.5, though cities can learn from each other, it is vital that each develops its own benchmarks and targets among the areas of need and opportunity. This development should be based on the individual mobility needs and challenges, and diverse elements such as density, existing infrastructure, climate, topography, etc. (Cohen, 2012). Once these considerations are established, the current chapter is focused on the transferability of the strategies applied in Merida in terms of Smart City approach to enhance Active Mobility. These strategies could be mirrored in different intermediate cities around the world.

Merida's success can be attributed to several key factors.

The city carried out diverse diagnostic processes, where areas of opportunity and risks were identified. Examples of these diagnostic efforts are present at the Cyclocities Ranking 2021, the Integral Plan for Sustainable Urban Mobility (PIMUS) 2040 for Mérida, and the Bases and Strategies to Strengthen the use of bicycles for sustainable mobility (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 174).

Merida has also created institutions focused on specific aspects of urban development and mobility, such as the Institute for Mobility and Urban-Territorial Development (Ibidem.).

Merida has a strong legal framework towards sustainability and sustainable mobility. At the international level, Mexico has established diverse actions and policies towards sustainability. For example, its commitment to the Paris Agreement and the Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC) at COP21, COP27 and COP28 (Gobierno de México, 2023, pp. 4–5). At the national level, the creation of the General Climate Change Law (LGCC). (Mexico - Gobierno de la República, 2015, p. 6, 9) and the reform to the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States recognizing the right of bicycles to be used as a means of mobility (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 25) are examples of this cohesive framework towards sustainable mobility.

At the local level, the integration of society with experts at the design process has also been a strategy that has promoted acceptance among citizens, while encouraging the integration of Active Mobility in public mobility policies. the non-motorized mobility plan for the metropolitan area of Mérida published in 2016 (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 174). Parallel actions included the construction of bike lanes, bike-sharing systems, and the promotion of bicycle use through bicycle rides, campaigns, bicycle schools, recreational bike lanes (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 25). These actions are examples provide the legal framework to develop projects who aim to sustainable urban development.

Merida has also embraced a holistic approach that extends beyond mobility, going through economic, social, and environmental sustainability. Va y Ven system is an example, where the enhancement of public transport and intermodality (walking and bicycle use) (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2023) promote sustainable and environmentally friendly transportation. Additionally, the differentiated tariffs and charges per kilometer (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2024d) serve to advance towards social equity within the transportation system.

The City has also taken advantage of the national funds, and has destined part of the Federal Expenditure Budget to resources for sustainable urban mobility (Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 39). Additionally, the city has also benefited from international funding. Such is the case of the technical assistance grant provided by the U.S. Trade and Development Agency to modernize the public transportation system in Merida (U.S. Trade and Development Agency, 2022).

Merida has also established national and international cooperation, not only through

funding mechanisms, but also through partnerships for education and exchange in platforms such as the Smart City Expo Latam Congress (SCELC). This brings opportunities for collaboration at a national and international level, with both public and private actors, research institutes and universities that can help implement viable actions that guarantee real impacts that contribute to generate more sustainable, technological, and inclusive societies (SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V., 2023) (Abraham *et al.*, 2017, pp. 19–20). It also allows to learn from the best practices applied in other cities (Cisneros, 2024).

Merida City has recognized, understood and used its geography to promote active mobility and take advantage of sustainable energy sources to power Smart City technologies, such as WiFi network (Cisneros, 2024). Merida's flat surface allows to implement Active Mobility in a comfortable setting. The city's strong winds as well as solar capacity can also produce solar and eolic power through solar panels and wind turbines (Cisneros, 2024).

Merida has also improved and extended its existent infrastructure in both Active Mobility and Smart City approaches. Through the creation of cycling lanes and increase of sidewalks, active mobility is enhanced (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 171-173). While through the creation of the C5i and the expansion and improvement of existing lightning and electricity poles, the way is paved for the installation of WiFi, cameras, panic buttons and similar technologies that can improve the safety perception for pedestrians, cyclists, and overall mobility users (Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, 2022) (Cisneros, 2024).

One milestone achieved by Merida City was the political endorsement of mobility projects and the call for expanding the cycling infrastructure network. During the 2021 election campaign, diverse candidates would support active mobility projects despite the party affiliations (Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 171).

Another relevant aspect is the city's cultural strength rooted in its Mayan heritage, that acts as a foundation that supports the transformative impacts of technology and its assimilation. When digitalized networks, such as 5G, are implemented, society accepts the strong technological change because it is prepared to withstand its impact without making vulnerable its identity and culture. Tradition and progress coexist in the city, what provides Merida with a competitive advantage that show how technological evolution can complement cultural heritage without compromising either (Cisneros, 2024).

The key factors that have contributed to Merida's success in the enhancement of Active Mobility through the Smart City approach can be summarized as follows:

1. Diagnostic process
2. Holistic approach: social, economic, and environmental
3. Legal framework – National, International and Local
 - a. Sustainability and Sustainable mobility
4. Institutions focused on specific aspects of urban development and mobility
5. National and international
 - a. Funding
 - b. Cooperation and education
6. Understanding and use of its geography
 - a. Active Mobility
 - b. Sustainable energy sources
7. Improvement and expansion of existing infrastructure
 - a. For Active Mobility
 - b. For safety perception through Smart City technologies
8. Civil society involvement
 - a. Bicycle routes
9. Political endorsement to mobility issues
10. Resilience in embracing digital advancements
 - a. Coexistence deep rooted Mayan culture and identity with technological transformations
11. Experts and citizens participation
12. Integration in Policies
 - a. National
 - b. Local
13. Active Mobility and Smart City projects
 - a. Inclusion in policies
 - b. Implementation

In conclusion, Merida's actions to achieve sustainable mobility through the enhancement of Active Mobility through a Smart City approach offer possibilities and insights for cities throughout the globe. By the promotion of individual strategies for specific needs, collaboration can be promoted through a holistic approach that considers social, economic, and environmental sustainability. Collaboration at local, national, and international levels can help integrate technological advancements within a resilient cultural framework. Merida's strategies serve as an inspiration to demonstrate that balance between progress and cultural heritage is feasible and advantageous in enhancing the mobility infrastructure and building a sustainable future for cities worldwide.

9 Conclusions

This research project had as its main goal to establish how Smart Mobility approaches can be integrated into the urban transport system to promote and enhance Active Mobility in a middle-sized or intermediate city in an emerging country, such as Merida in Mexico. Secondary research questions were posed, including “*What is Smart Mobility within the Smart City Approach?*”, “*How can Smart City technologies improve cycling infrastructure and safety in Merida?*”, and “*What Smart City technologies can be used to improve pedestrian infrastructure and encourage walking as a mode of transport in Merida?*”.

To answer the research questions, a mixed-method approach was adopted. First, literature review was consulted to establish a common framework on the concepts Sustainability, Smart City, Mobility, Transport, Sustainable Transport, Sustainable Mobility, Smart Mobility and Active Mobility. Afterwards, an analysis was made to understand in general terms how can Smart City approach enhance Active Mobility. Afterwards, media review, expert interviews, discourse analysis and policy analysis were conducted to establish the current state of mobility and Smart City approach in the case study. First, approaching the national context of Mexico as a country, then focusing on the regional south-east context, and finally, centering on Yucatan State and Merida City as local context. Once this stage was completed, the next section analyzes how Smart City approach enhances Active Mobility in Merida City. At this point are established the potential applications and areas of opportunity for Merida City. Finally, the Analysis and Transferability are performed and summarized the strategies that Merida City has implemented to promote Active Mobility through a Smart City Approach, and how these strategies can be applied and implemented in similar contexts throughout the world.

At the global level, world’s population living in urban areas is increasing, risking the sustainability of the system and its social, economic, and environmental resources. This has led to the creation of different approaches to face urban challenges in a sustainable way where development meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Among these urban challenges are those related with infrastructure and mobility. Consequently, the Smart City, Sustainable Mobility, Smart Mobility and Active Mobility approaches have raised.

The Smart City approach aims to deal with global energy consumption, CO2 emissions and growing population in urban agglomerations through the use of ICT technologies with a social, economic, and environmental approach. On the other hand, Active Mobility promotes transport via non-motorized vehicles, such as walking and cycling, either solely or in combination with public transport. Though they are different concepts and part from different bases, their common objective for sustainable development makes it possible for them to work in collaboration and complement each other.

In terms of the question “*What is Smart Mobility as an element of Smart City?*”, the answer highlights that Mobility itself focuses on the movement within urban context, and Smart Mobility takes advantage of the potential of information exchange and connectivity to create user-oriented transport systems, where through the adoption of smart technologies, real-time responses are implemented to changing patterns of traffic behaviour, and contributing to the implementation of sustainable and climate-friendly modes of transport.

Some examples of strategies where Active and Smart Mobility combine, are the following. The integrated transport system where Smart Mobility solutions integrate a network with diverse modes of transport. Another example is the provision of real-time information regarding public transport schedules, traffic conditions, and alternative routes. The integration of smart public lighting, smart crosswalks, cyclist-friendly navigation apps, and bike sharing systems are also strategies where these elements connect. From a policy perspective, the establishment of geo-fences to create zero-emission zones is also an innovative way to approach mobility from a Smart City approach. Finally, collaborative platforms to share resources and the use of digital communication channels to raise public awareness are also strategies.

At the national level, in the twentieth century Mexico opened its economy to the global arena and the market expansion, transitioning into an Emerging country that transformed the country's urban landscape. Nowadays approximately 81% of the Mexican population resides in Urban areas. However, the development in the country has been unequal and the northern and central part of the country have had a higher development than the southern region. It is under this context that a decentralization project takes place, putting in the spot infrastructure development projects that bring resources, investment, population growth and higher demand for services, and local infrastructure to the south-eastern cities. Among these cities is Merida, the biggest and most populated city in the region. Merida is also the venue for the Smart City Expo Latam Congress and has been an outstanding city at the Cyclocities Ranking 2021.

It is under this umbrella that Merida City becomes a referent when talking about Smart City approach to enhance Active Mobility. Through diverse actions, the answers to the questions unravel: "*How can Smart City technologies improve cycling infrastructure and safety in Merida?*" and "*What Smart City technologies can be used to improve pedestrian infrastructure and encourage walking as a mode of transport in Merida?*". Merida has implemented diverse projects with both perspectives. An example of the promotion of walking and cycling project, is the Complete Street: Paseo de Montejo. Roadways were re-designed, redistributed and operated. The project included the construction and/or rehabilitation of sidewalks, ramps, and sidewalk lining, as well as narrowing vehicle lanes to implement a cycle lane with buoys, redesigning of intersections, installation of bike racks, pedestrian traffic lights, and assistance lights. This, in combination with the smart street lights and the monitoring systems for security and traffic at C5i, provide safety, accessibility, and healthy travel for pedestrians, cyclists and overall street users. Other examples are implementation of the Mobility as a Service Bicycle shared system (En Bici) and the digitalization of public transport (Va y Ven), as well as the promotion of intermodality through the integration of bike racks to public transportation units. Investment also has played a major role at national and international level. Through funding mechanisms such as the USTDA technical assistance, that aims to advance the deployment of intelligent transportation system (ITS) technologies and electric mobility solutions across the city, as well as to enhance overall system performance, bus control and monitoring operations and safety, while advancing the transition to electric buses for Mérida's public transportation fleet. Through these funding mechanisms, the infrastructure of the city can be improved through the modernization and implementation of smart mobility in the city, encouraging walking and cycling as safe, comfortable, and efficient transport modes. The installation of the citizen's council for the promotion of bicycle use in the metropolitan area of Merida also plays an indirect role when promoting active and smart mobility, especially cycling. Its focus on generating data on cycling infrastructure also promote the improvement and expansion of the existing infrastructure, specially the smart one. Last, but not least, forums to exchange and share best practices such as the SCELIC, are necessary to continue innovating and finding new implementations of smart technologies and approaches to promote walking, cycling and overall Active Mobility.

These strategies are highlights not only for the city, but for the south-east region.

However, the city still has areas of opportunity where further work can be taken towards the final goal. For example, consolidating a Smart City strategy at local or regional level, increasing the Complete Street projects throughout the city, using natural resources to produce sustainable energy to power Smart City technologies, increasing the features in existing infrastructure, taking advantage of the geography to apply new technologies, and creating user-friendly platforms.

It is in this context that the Research Question is answered: *How can Smart Mobility approaches be integrated into the urban transport system to promote and enhance Active Mobility options in a city of an emerging country such as Mexico, in the case of Merida?* Smart Mobility approaches can be integrated into the urban transport system to promote and enhance Active Mobility options in Merida through diverse strategies. It is notable that these strategies implemented in the Merida context can be applied in similar contexts globally. These strategies are: elaborating diagnostic process, having a holistic approach

(social, economic and environmental), consolidating a legal framework at different levels (national, international, and local) based on sustainability and sustainable mobility, promoting national and international cooperation, education, and funding, understanding and using of its geography in terms of Active Mobility and sustainable energy sources, improving and expanding the existing infrastructure (for Active Mobility and Smart City technologies), civil society involvement, political endorsement to mobility issues, resilience in embracing digital advancements and coexistence between the deep rooted Mayan culture and identity with technological transformations, experts and citizens participation, the integration in national and local policies, and the Active Mobility and Smart City projects itself, their inclusion in policies and their implementation.

Based on these points, Merida City and the strategies used to enhance Active Mobility through a Smart City approach can serve as a reference for cities with similar characteristics throughout the world.

10 List of References

Abraham, M. *et al.* (2017) 'Smart City: The importance of the current discourse for the work at the Center for Technology and Society.', *Center for Technology and Society*, 37/2017.

Agencia Digital de Innovación Pública (2018) *Acerca de la Ciudad de México*. México: Gobierno de México. Available at: <https://mexicocity.cdmx.gob.mx/e/about/about-mexico-city/?lang=es> (Accessed: 6 September 2023).

Agencia EFE (2023) 'La octava edición de Smart City Expo LATAM Congress rompe récord en México'. Available at: <https://es-us.finanzas.yahoo.com/noticias/octava-edici%C3%B3n-smart-city-expo-234748041.html> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Albino, V., Berardi, U. and Dangelico, R.M. (2015) 'Smart Cities: Definitions, Dimensions, Performance, and Initiatives', *Journal of Urban Technology*, 22(1), pp. 3–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2014.942092>.

Alfonzo, M.A. (2005) 'To Walk or Not to Walk? The Hierarchy of Walking Needs', *Environment and Behaviour*, 37(6), pp. 808–836. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916504274016>.

Algorithmic Objective Corp. (2023) 'What are the C2, C4, and C5 and why are they important?', *Algotive*. Available at: https://www.algotive.ai/blog/what-are-the-c2-c4-and-c5-and-why-are-they-important#ancla_1 (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Allwinkle, S. and Cruickshank, P. (2011) 'Creating Smart-er Cities: An Overview', *Journal of Urban Technology*, 18(2), pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2011.601103>.

Amazon Web Services (2023) 'What is IoT (Internet of Things)?' Available at: https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/iot/?nc1=h_ls (Accessed: 26 December 2023).

Arellana, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Urban walkability considering pedestrians' perceptions of the built environment: a 10-year review and a case study in a medium-sized city in Latin America', *Transport Reviews*, 40(2), pp. 183–203. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2019.1703842>.

Arndt, W.-H. (2024) 'Interview on Smart City approach in Mérida, México. (Zoom meeting). Interview with Wulf-Holger Arndt, Head of Area „Mobility and Space" Center for Technology and Society'.

Ayuntamiento de Mérida (2016) 'Plan Maestro para la Movilidad Urbana Sustentable'. Available at: <https://isla.merida.gob.mx/serviciosinternet/ordenamientoterritorial/docs/PlanMaestroMUS.pdf> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

Ayuntamiento de Mérida (2023) 'En Bici', *Movilidad Municipal*. Available at: <https://www.merida.gob.mx/movilidad/en-bici.php> (Accessed: 13 January 2024).

Banco Nacional de Obras y Servicios Públicos, S.N.C. (2023) 'Obras y su impacto social: Va y Ven, sistema integral de transporte sustentable (Primera Etapa)', *Gobierno de México*. Available at: <https://www.gob.mx/banobras/articulos/obras-y-su-impacto-social-va-y-ven-sistema-integral-de-transporte-sustentable-primera-etapa> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Bauman, A.E. *et al.* (2012) 'Correlates of physical activity: why are some people physically active and others not?', *The Lancet*, 380(9838), pp. 258–271. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)60735-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60735-1).

Blázquez, J. and Santiso, J. (2003) *México, ¿un ex-emergente?* 0301. Mexico: BBVA Research, p. 1. Available at: https://www.bbva.com/wp-content/uploads/migrados/WP_0301_tcm346-212393.pdf (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Bundesministerium des Innern (2009) 'National Strategy for Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP Strategy)'. Available at: https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/downloads/EN/publikationen/2009/kritis_englisch.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1 (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Caccia, L. (2019) '5 exemplos de caminhabilidade', *WRI BRASIL*. Available at: <https://www.wribrasil.org.br/noticias/5-exemplos-de-caminhabilidade> (Accessed: 28 December 2023).

Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión (2023) 'Ley General de Movilidad y Seguridad Vial', *DOF 08-05-2023*. Available at: <https://www.diputados.gob.mx/LeyesBiblio/pdf/LGMSV.pdf> (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Caragliu, A., Del Bo, C. and Nijkamp, P. (2011) 'Smart Cities in Europe', *Journal of Urban Technology*, 18(2), pp. 65–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2011.601117>.

CEPAL (2014) 'Implementation of Rio+20'. Available at: <https://www.cepal.org/rio20/en/index> (Accessed: 15 December 2023).

Cervero, R. and Kockelman, K. (1997) 'Travel demand and the 3Ds: Density, diversity, and design', *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 2(3), pp. 199–219. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1361-9209\(97\)00009-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1361-9209(97)00009-6).

Chiradeja, P. and Yoomak, S. (2023) 'Development of public lighting system with smart lighting control systems and internet of thing (IoT) technologies for smart city', *Energy Reports*, 10, pp. 3355–3372. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.10.027>.

Cisneros, E. (2024) 'Interview on Active Mobility and Smart City approach. Case study: Mérida, México. (Whatsapp recording). Interview with Elías Cisneros, former Presidente of the Colegio Yucateco de Arquitectos, A.C.'

Cohen, B. (2012) 'What Exactly is a Smart City?', *Fast Company*. Available at: <https://www.fastcompany.com/1680538/what-exactly-is-a-smart-city> (Accessed: 26 December 2023).

Curtis, C. and Scheurer, J. (2010) 'Planning for sustainable accessibility: Developing tools to aid discussion and decision-making', *Progress in Planning*, 74(2), pp. 53–106. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progress.2010.05.001>.

De Geus, B. *et al.* (2012) 'A prospective cohort study on minor accidents involving commuter cyclists in Belgium', *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 45, pp. 683–693. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2011.09.045>.

Deutscher Städtetag (2015) 'Integrierte Stadtentwicklungsplanung und Stadtentwicklungsmanagement. Positionspapier des Deutschen Städtetages'. Available at: <https://www.staedtetag.de/files/dst/docs/Publikationen/Positionspapiere/Archiv/integrierte-stadtentwicklungsplanung-positionspapier-2015.pdf> (Accessed: 24 December 2024).

DiDi (2019) 'DiDi abre un nuevo Club de Conductores en Mérida'. Available at: <https://web.didiglobal.com/mx/newsroom/didi-abre-un-nuevo-club-de-conductores-en-merida/> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Einfeldt, C. *et al.* (2013) 'Resilienz als Paradigma der Stadtentwicklung – Nutzen und

Chancen für Städte in Deutschland und der Welt', *Stiftung neue verantwortung*, 8/13. Available at: https://www.stiftung-nv.de/sites/default/files/13_08_policy_brief_urban_infrastructure_management.pdf (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc. (2024) 'Cenote'. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/science/cenote> (Accessed: 21 January 2024).

EurActiv (2014) 'Oettinger startet europäische „Smart Cities“-Initiative'. Available at: <https://www.euractiv.de/section/stadt-der-zukunft/news/oettinger-startet-europaische-smart-cities-initiative/> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Farfán, E. (2021) 'Arranca la ruta "Va y Ven", nuevo servicio de transporte en Mérida', *PorEsto!* Available at: <https://www.poresto.net/yucatan/2021/11/27/arranca-la-ruta-va-ven-nuevo-servicio-de-transporte-en-merida-300594.html> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Fernández, V. (2015) 'Mérida, con sistema de transporte urbano de vanguardia', *Artículo 7*. Available at: <https://a7.com.mx/index.php?notaid=50865> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Frost, S. (2015) 'Smart City: Wie neue Technik die Städte verändert', *TAGESSPIEGEL*. Available at: <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/wirtschaft/wie-neue-technik-die-stadte-verandert-3627760.html> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

García-Tejeda, E. (2016) 'La regulación de Uber en la Ciudad de México, la ganancia de los consumidores y el problema público de la movilidad'. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349008031_La_regulacion_de_Uber_en_la_Ciudad_de_Mexico_la_ganancia_de_los_consumidores_y_el_problema_publico_de_la_movilidad (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Geoportal de Mérida Yucatán (2023) 'Mérida - Geomorfología'. Available at: <https://geoportal.merida.gob.mx/> (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Gerike, R. *et al.* (2016) 'Physical Activity through Sustainable Transport Approaches (PASTA): a study protocol for a multicentre project', *BMJ Open*, 6(1), p. e009924. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-009924>.

Giffinger, R. *et al.* (2007) 'Smart cities - Ranking of European medium-sized cities', pp. 10–11.

Global Climate Change Action (2020) 'CLIMATE ACTION PATHWAY - TRANSPORT. Executive Summary'. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Climate%20Action%20Pathway%20Transport.%20Executive%20Summary.pdf> (Accessed: 27 December 2023).

Global Climate Change Action (2021) 'CLIMATE ACTION PATHWAY - TRANSPORT. Action Table'. Available at: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Transport_ActionTable_2.1.pdf (Accessed: 27 December 2023).

Gobierno de la Ciudad de México (2023) '¿Qué es Ecobici?', *ECOBICI*. Available at: <https://ecobici.cdmx.gob.mx/conoce-sistema/> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Gobierno de la Ciudad de México (2024a) 'Centro de Comando, Control, Cómputo, Comunicaciones y Contacto Ciudadano de la Ciudad de México'. Available at: <https://www.c5.cdmx.gob.mx/dependencia/acerca-de#:~:text=El%20Centro%20de%20Comando%2C%20Control,ambiente%2C%20protecci%C3%B3n%20civil%2C%20movilidad%20y> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Gobierno de la Ciudad de México (2024b) 'Internet gratuito: Un derecho para todas y todos en espacios públicos de la Ciudad de México'. Available at: <https://gobierno.cdmx.gob.mx/noticias/internet-gratuito-un-derecho-para-todas-y-todos-en-espacios-publicos-de-la-ciudad-de-mexico/> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Gobierno de México (2022a) '4 INFORME DE GOBIERNO 2021-2022', *Presidencia de la República*. Available at: <https://framework-gb.cdn.gob.mx/informe/5b8e7a983a893dfcbd02a8e444abfb45.pdf> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Gobierno de México (2022b) 'Contribución Determinada a nivel Nacional. Actualización 2022. (English: Nationally Determined Contribution. Update 2022)', pp. 11–12.

Gobierno de México (2023) 'Documento de posición de México para la COP28'. Available at: https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/873838/Documento_breve_de_posicio_n_de_Me_xico_para_la_COP28.pdf (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Gobierno de México. Secretaría de Medio Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (2020) 'Contribución Determinada a nivel Nacional: México. Versión actualizada 2020.' Available at: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/NDC-Esp-30Dic.pdf> (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Gobierno de Yucatán (2021) 'Presentan el Gobernador Mauricio Vila Dosal y el alcalde, Renán Barrera Concha, Programa Conjunto de Mejora a la Movilidad y la Infraestructura Vial en Mérida'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/saladeprensa/ver_notas.php?id=4228 (Accessed: 13 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2010) 'Mérida'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/estado/ver_municipio.php?id=50 (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2016) 'PLAN DE MOVILIDAD URBANA NO MOTORIZADA PARA LA ZONA METROPOLITANA DE MÉRIDA'. Available at: <https://acervo.yucatan.gob.mx/contenidos/PMUNM-ZMM.pdf> (Accessed: 12 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2021a) 'Avanza construcción del Centro de Control, Comando, Comunicaciones, Cómputo, Coordinación e Inteligencia (C5i) de Yucatán'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/saladeprensa/ver_notas.php?id=4986 (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2021b) 'Indicadores del Inegi confirman que Yucatán es de los estados con mayor calidad de vida del país'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/saladeprensa/ver_notas.php?id=4156#:~:text=Indicadores%20del%20Inegi%20confirman%20que,calidad%20de%20vida%20del%20pa%C3%ADs&text=Directivos%20de%20ese%20organismo%20aut%C3%B3nomo,a%20titular%20de%20la%20SSG. (Accessed: 6 September 2023).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2022) 'Inaugura el Gobernador Mauricio Vila Dosal el centro C5i de Yucatán para fortalecer la coordinación y seguridad en el estado'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/saladeprensa/ver_notas.php?id=5765 (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2023a) 'Municipios de Yucatán'. Available at: <https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/estado/municipios.php> (Accessed: 5 January 2023).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2023b) 'Yucatán mantiene su posición como la entidad

más segura del país'. Available at: https://www.yucatan.gob.mx/saladeprensa/ver_notas.php?id=7262 (Accessed: 12 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024a) 'Biciruta Mérida', p. Biciruta.

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024b) 'Calidad del aire'. Available at: <https://aire.yucatan.gob.mx/estaciones> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024c) 'ESTRATEGIA INTEGRAL DEL SISTEMA DE TRANSPORTE PÚBLICO VA Y VEN'. Available at: <https://vayven.yucatan.gob.mx/> (Accessed: 18 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024d) 'NUEVAS RUTAS CENTRO-CAUCEL'. Available at: <https://vayven.yucatan.gob.mx/files/get/148> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024e) 'Plan de infraestructura de ciclovías', p. Ciclovías.

Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2024f) 'RUTAS VA Y VEN'. Available at: <https://vayven.yucatan.gob.mx/rutas-va-y-ven> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Gobierno México (2023) 'Laboratorios Urbanos: Interconectando Ciudades Inteligentes'. Available at: <https://portales.sre.gob.mx/dgvosc/programas/laboratorios-urbanos-ici> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Goytia, M.J. (2022) 'Merida Will Host Smart City Expo LATAM for 3rd Year In A Row', *Mexico Business News*. Available at: <https://mexicobusiness.news/infrastructure/news/merida-will-host-smart-city-expo-latam-3rd-year-row> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

GreenBiz Editors (2009) 'IBM and Cisco to Help Amsterdam Become a "Smart City"'. Available at: <https://www.greenbiz.com/article/ibm-and-cisco-help-amsterdam-become-smart-city> (Accessed: 18 December 2023).

Griffor, E. (2017) *Handbook of System Safety and Security*. Elsevier. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2014-0-05033-2>.

Grupo Banco Mundial (2023) *Población urbana (% del total) - Mexico*. Available at: <https://datos.bancomundial.org/indicador/SP.URB.TOTL.IN.ZS?locations=MX> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Guarneros Olmos, F. (2023) 'México tiene ciudades en camino a ser smart, pero les falta infraestructura', 2023. *Expansión*. Available at: <https://expansion.mx/tecnologia/2023/04/26/mexico-smart-cities-sin-infraestructura#:~:text=%C2%BFEn%20M%C3%A9xico%20hay%20ciudades%20inteligentes,y%20Smart%20City%20en%20Puebla.> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Halpern, D. (2005) *Social capital*. Cambridge, UK ; Malden, MA: Polity.

Handy, S., Van Wee, B. and Kroesen, M. (2014) 'Promoting Cycling for Transport: Research Needs and Challenges', *Transport Reviews*, 34(1), pp. 4–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2013.860204>.

Hernández, L. (2019) 'AMLO pone fin a Zonas Económicas Especiales', *El Economista*. Available at: <https://www.economista.com.mx/estados/AMLO-pone-fin-a-Zonas-Economicas-Especiales-20190426-0026.html> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

HLAG-ST (2016) 'Mobilizing Sustainable Transport for Development. Analysis and Policy

Recommendations from the United Nations Secretary-General's High-Level Advisory Group on Sustainable Transport'. Available at: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/2375Mobilizing%20Sustainable%20Transport.pdf> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

Höjer, M. and Wangel, J. (2015) 'Smart Sustainable Cities: Definition and Challenges', in L.M. Hilty and B. Aebischer (eds) *ICT Innovations for Sustainability*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing), pp. 333–349. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-09228-7_20.

Hollands, R.G. (2008) 'Will the real smart city please stand up?: Intelligent, progressive or entrepreneurial?', *City*, 12(3), pp. 303–320. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604810802479126>.

Hopfner, K. and Zakrzewski, P. (2012) 'Nachhaltige Quartiersentwicklung im Bestand', in M. Drilling and O. Schnur (eds) *Nachhaltige Quartiersentwicklung*. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, pp. 45–67. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-531-94150-9_2.

INEGI (2020) 'Censo de Población y Vivienda 2020', *Información de México para niños*. Available at: <https://www.inegi.org.mx/programas/ccpv/2020/> (Accessed: 11 January 2024).

INEGI (2021) 'Población total por entidad federativa y grupo quinquenal de edad según sexo, serie de años censales de 1990 a 2020'. Available at: https://www.inegi.org.mx/app/tabulados/interactivos/?pxq=Poblacion_Poblacion_01_e60cd8cf-927f-4b94-823e-972457a12d4b (Accessed: 4 January 2024).

INEGI (2023) 'Clima', *Información de México para niños*. Available at: <https://cuentame.inegi.org.mx/monografias/informacion/yuc/territorio/clima.aspx> (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

INEGI (2024) 'Extensión territorial.', *Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía*. Available at: <https://cuentame.inegi.org.mx/territorio/extension/default.aspx?tema=T> (Accessed: 4 January 2024).

Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México (2023) 'Mejores Calles para México™'. Available at: <https://mexico.itdp.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/mcx-libro-completo-DIGITAL-Baja.pdf> (Accessed: 12 January 2024).

Instituto Municipal de Planeación (2020) 'PIMUS MÉRIDA 2040. PLAN INTEGRAL DE MOVILIDAD URBANA'. Available at: https://isla.merida.gob.mx/serviciosinternet/ordenamientoterritorial/docs/PIMUS_2040.pdf (Accessed: 12 January 2024).

International Council on Clean Transportation (2020) 'VISION 2050 - A strategy to decarbonize the global transport sector by mid-century', p. 12.

International Transport Forum | OECD (2021) 'Worldwide transport activity to double, emissions to rise further'. Available at: <https://www.itf-oecd.org/worldwide-transport-activity-double-emissions-rise-further> (Accessed: 27 December 2023).

Iteris, Inc. (2023) 'Iteris Chosen To Support Intelligent Transportation Systems Project In Mérida, Mexico'. Available at: <https://www.iteris.com/news/iteris-chosen-support-intelligent-transportation-systems-project-merida-mexico> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

Jangade, S. (2021) 'The Rise of Emerging 7 as a Global Powerhouse in the coming years', *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH*. Available at: <https://ijsdr.org/papers/IJSDR2105059.pdf> (Accessed: 4 January 2024).

Khor, N. (2022) *World cities report 2022: envisaging the future of cities*. Nairobi, Kenya: United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat). Available at: https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2022/06/wcr_2022.pdf (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Koszowski, C. *et al.* (2019) 'Active Mobility: Bringing Together Transport Planning, Urban Planning, and Public Health', in B. Müller and G. Meyer (eds) *Towards User-Centric Transport in Europe*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Lecture Notes in Mobility), pp. 149–171. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99756-8_11.

Kourtit, K. and Nijkamp, P. (2012) 'Smart cities in the innovation age', *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 25(2), pp. 93–95. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2012.660331>.

Laimer, C. (2014) 'Smart Cities - Zurück in die Zukunft', *Dérive* [Preprint], (56). Available at: <https://derive.at/texte/smart-cities-zuruck-in-die-zukunft/> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Lee, Q.Y. and Pojani, D. (2019) 'Making cycling irresistible in tropical climates? Views from Singapore', *Policy Design and Practice*, 2(4), pp. 359–369. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2019.1665857>.

Lindskog, H. (2004) 'Smart communities initiatives'. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228371789_Smart_communities_initiatives (Accessed: 18 December 2023).

López Obrador, A.M. (2017) 'Explica AMLO la descentralización del gobierno', *Youtube*. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BBMOI18fs9o> (Accessed: 6 September 2023).

Maldonado Silveira Alonso Munhoz, P.A. *et al.* (2020) 'Smart Mobility: The Main Drivers for Increasing the Intelligence of Urban Mobility', *Sustainability*, 12(24), p. 10675. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410675>.

McKinsey & Company (2019) 'How can the private and public sectors work together to create smart cities?' Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/operations/our-insights/how-can-the-private-and-public-sectors-work-together-to-create-smart-cities> (Accessed: 18 January 2024).

Mela, G. and Girardi, P. (2022) 'Health effects of active mobility and their economic value: Unit benefit factor estimates for Italy', *El Sevier*, 26(101487), p. 1,2.

Merforth, M. (2023) 'Cycling in the Heat: Overcoming Challenges and Promoting Sustainable Mobility', *Urbanet*. Available at: <https://www.urbanet.info/cycling-heat-sustainable-mobility/> (Accessed: 28 January 2024).

Mexico - Gobierno de la República (2015) 'INTENDED NATIONALLY DETERMINED CONTRIBUTION'. Available at: https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/162973/2015_indc_ing.pdf (Accessed: 5 January 2024).

Mezei, J.I. and Lázanyi, K. (2018) 'Are We Ready for Smart Transport? Analysis of Attitude Towards Public Transport in Budapest', *Interdisciplinary Description of Complex Systems*, 16(3), pp. 369–375. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7906/indec.16.3.9>.

Mobility Lab (2018) 'Mobility Doesn't Mean The Same Thing As Transportation'. Available at: <https://mobilitylab.org/transportation-demand-management/further-reading/mobility-doesnt-mean-the-same-thing-as-transportation/> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

Modeshift (2023) 'What Is The Difference Between Transportation And Mobility?' Available at: <https://www.modeshift.com/what-is-the-difference-between-transportation-and-mobility/> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

Mohieldin, M. and Vandycke, N. (2017) 'Sustainable Mobility for the 21st Century'. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2017/07/10/sustainable-mobility-for-the-21st-century> (Accessed: 26 December 2023).

Mörsch, T. (2015) 'Horizont 2020: Europäische Smart-City Leuchtturmprojekte', *Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung*. Available at: <https://www.kooperation-international.de/aktuelles/nachrichten/detail/info/horizont-2020-europaeische-smart-city-leuchtturmprojekte> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Müller-Eie, D. and Kosmidis, I. (2023) 'Sustainable mobility in smart cities: a document study of mobility initiatives of mid-sized Nordic smart cities', *European Transport Research Review*, 15(1), p. 36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-023-00610-4>.

Nam, T. and Pardo, T.A. (2011) 'Conceptualizing smart city with dimensions of technology, people, and institutions', in *Proceedings of the 12th Annual International Digital Government Research Conference: Digital Government Innovation in Challenging Times. dg.o '11: The 12th Annual International Conference of Digital Government Research*, College Park Maryland USA: ACM, pp. 282–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2037556.2037602>.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2022) 'Urban population by city size'. Available at: <https://data.oecd.org/popregion/urban-population-by-city-size.htm#:~:text=Urban%20areas%20in%20OECD%20countries,areas%20if%20their%20population%20is> (Accessed: 11 January 2024).

Paskaleva, K.A. (2011) 'The smart city: A nexus for open innovation?', *Intelligent Buildings International*, 3(3), pp. 153–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508975.2011.586672>.

Patiño Pastrana, J.A. (2015) 'Centro de Estudios Demográficos, Urbanos y Ambientales, A.C.', *El Colegio de México*. Available at: <https://cedua.colmex.mx/archivos/521/a76-jose-antonio-patin%20B3o-pastrana.pdf> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Pendyala, R.M., Bhat, C.R. and International Association for Travel Behaviour Research (eds) (2012) *Travel behaviour research in an evolving world: selected papers from the 12th International Conference on Travel Behaviour Research; [Jaipur, Rajasthan, INDIA, December 13-18, 2009]*. 1. ed. [Raleigh, NC: Lulu Publ.].

Pérez Campos, A., García Romero, L. and Medina Martínez, I. (2021) 'Ranking Ciclociudades 2021', *Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y el Desarrollo*. Available at: https://ciclociudades.s3.us-west-2.amazonaws.com/Ranking%20Ciclociudades%202021_highres_16082022.pdf (Accessed: 28 December 2023).

Prefeitura do Rio de Janeiro (2012) 'Plano Estratégico da Prefeitura do Rio de Janeiro 2013-2016. PÓS 2016. O Rio mais integrado e competitivo', pp. 64–67.

Realcom Antenas y Torres (2024) 'Arcos Carreteros'. Available at: <https://realcom.com.mx/producto/arcos-carreteros/> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Rodrigue, J.-P. (2020) *The Geography of Transport Systems*. 5th edn. Fifth edition. | Abingdon, Oxon; New York, NY: Routledge, 2020.: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429346323>.

Rodríguez, Ó. (2017) 'Uber, bajo la ley de transporte en Yucatán', *La Jornada Maya*, 25

- May. Available at: <https://www.lajornadamaya.mx/yucatan/149320/uber-bajo-la-ley-de-transporte-en-yucatan> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).
- Rohde, F. and Loew, T. (2011) 'Smart City: Begriff, Charakteristika und Beispiele', *Materialien der Wiener Stadtwerke zur nachhaltigen Entwicklung*, (7), pp. 1–10.
- Romero Ocampo, M. de L. (2019) *Geografía. Cuarto grado*. Cuarta edición. México, D.F.: Secretaría de Educación Pública.
- Romm, D. et al. (2022) 'Differences in first-mile and last-mile behaviour in candidate multi-modal Boston bike-share micromobility trips', *Journal of Transport Geography*, 102, pp. 1–3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103370>.
- Ruiz, I. and Tigre, A. (2014) 'Smart Cities beyond technology: management and planning for urban innovation In: Ciudades Inteligentes e Mobilidade Urbana.', *CADERNOS. FGV PROJETOS*, (24), pp. 86–95.
- Rupprecht Consult (2019) 'SUMPS-UP. Update of the SUMP Guidelines.', *European Commission*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c8774a17&appId=PPGMS> (Accessed: 27 December 2023).
- Santiago, D. (2023) 'Con viajes gratis, anuncian "En Bici", el nuevo sistema de transporte de Mérida', *PorEsto!* Available at: <https://www.poresto.net/yucatan/2023/5/17/con-viajes-gratis-anuncian-en-bici-el-nuevo-sistema-de-transporte-de-merida-384188.html> (Accessed: 12 January 2024).
- Schipper, F., Emanuel, M. and Oldenziel, R. (2020) 'Sustainable Urban Mobility in the Present, Past, and Future', *Technology and Culture*, 61(1), pp. 307–317. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1353/tech.2020.0004>.
- Schweitzer, E. (2015) *Smart cities international: Strategien, Strukturen und Pilotvorhaben*. Bonn: Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung.
- Secretaría de Desarrollo Sustentable del Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán (2018) 'Sistema de monitoreo de la calidad del aire'. Available at: <https://sds.yucatan.gob.mx/calidad-aire/monitoreo-calidad-aire-yucatan.php> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).
- Secretaría de Gobernación (2019) 'Plan Nacional de Desarrollo 2019-2024', *Diario Oficial de la Federación*. Available at: https://www.dof.gob.mx/nota_detalle.php?codigo=5565599&fecha=12/07/2019#gsc.tab=0 (Accessed: 6 January 2024).
- Sengupta, R. (2022) 'What are Top Smart Urban Mobility Trends?', *Geospatial World*. Available at: <https://www.geospatialworld.net/prime/business-and-industry-trends/what-are-top-smart-urban-mobility-trends/#:~:text=An%20urban%20mobility%20trend%20with,no%20longer%20plays%20a%20role> (Accessed: 26 December 2023).
- Shelton, T., Zook, M. and Wiig, A. (2015) 'The "actually existing smart city"', *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 8(1), pp. 13–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsu026>.
- Silva, B.N., Khan, M. and Han, K. (2018) 'Towards sustainable smart cities: A review of trends, architectures, components, and open challenges in smart cities', *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 38, pp. 697–713. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.01.053>.
- Singer, N. (2012) 'Mission Control, Built for Cities', *New York Times*. Available at:

<https://www.nytimes.com/2012/03/04/business/ibm-takes-smarter-cities-concept-to-rio-de-janeiro.html> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

Soe, R.-M. (2017) 'FINEST Twins: platform for cross-border smart city solutions', in *Proceedings of the 18th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research, dg.o '17: 18th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research*, Staten Island NY USA: ACM, pp. 352–357. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3085228.3085287>.

Spik, D. (2022) 'What is geofencing for vehicles?', *Geotab Inc.* Available at: <https://www.geotab.com/blog/what-is-geofencing/> (Accessed: 18 January 2024).

SRE (2013) 'Información general sobre México', *Secretaría de Relaciones Exteriores.* Available at: <https://embamex.sre.gob.mx/republicadominicana/index.php/avisos/2-uncategorised/127-informacion-general-sobre-mexico> (Accessed: 4 January 2024).

Statista Research Department (2023) 'Annual average population in Mexico from 2015 to 2050'. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/726996/mexico-population/> (Accessed: 4 January 2024).

Sustainable Mobility for All (2022) *CATALOGUE OF POLICY MEASURES 2.0 - Toward Sustainable Mobility.* Washington, D.C. Available at: <https://www.sum4all.org/data/files/cpm20041822v6web.pdf>.

SUSTENTABILICITY S.A. de C.V (2023) 'Smart City Expo Latam Congress', *Pronus.* Available at: <https://smartcityexpolatam.com/evento/#:~:text=Celebrada%20en%20Barcelona%20desde%202011,urbana%20en%20todo%20el%20mundo.> (Accessed: 15 January 2024).

Tsunoda, K. *et al.* (2015) 'Transportation mode usage and physical, mental and social functions in older Japanese adults', *Journal of Transport & Health*, 2(1), pp. 44–49. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2014.10.003>.

UN-Habitat (2020a) 'ONU-Habitat analiza el impacto del Tren Maya'. Available at: <https://onuhabitat.org.mx/index.php/onu-habitat-analiza-el-impacto-del-tren-maya> (Accessed: 1 May 2024).

UN-Habitat (2020b) 'The New Urban Agenda'. Available at: <https://www.urbanagendaplatform.org/nua> (Accessed: 15 December 2023).

UN-Habitat (2023) 'Mobility and Transport'. Available at: <https://unhabitat.org/topic/mobility-and-transport> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

United Nations (2023a) 'The Sustainable Development Agenda'. Available at: <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/development-agenda/> (Accessed: 15 December 2023).

United Nations (2023b) 'Your guide to climate action: Transport', *Act Now.* Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/actnow/transport> (Accessed: 27 December 2023).

United Nations Climate Action (2023a) 'All about the NDCs'. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/all-about-ndcs#:~:text=NDCs%20are%20where%20countries%20set,so%20it%20stays%20on%20rack.> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

United Nations Climate Action (2023b) 'The Paris Agreement'. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/paris-agreement> (Accessed: 16 December 2023).

United Nations Climate Change (2015) 'Mexico Submits its Climate Action Plan Ahead of

2015 Paris Agreement'. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/news/mexico-submits-its-climate-action-plan-ahead-of-2015-paris-agreement> (Accessed: 16 December 2023).

United Nations Climate Change (2023) 'Paris Agreement - Status of Rectification'. Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process/the-paris-agreement/status-of-ratification> (Accessed: 16 December 2023).

United Nations Department for Economic and Social Affairs (2023) *Sustainable Development Goals Report 2023: Special Edition*. S.I.: UNITED NATIONS. Available at: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2023/The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2023.pdf> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2023a) 'Sustainable cities and human settlements'. Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/topics/sustainable-cities-and-human-settlements> (Accessed: 16 December 2023).

United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2023b) 'Sustainable transport', *Sustainable development*. Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/topics/sustainable-transport> (Accessed: 25 December 2023).

United Nations Treaty Collection (2015) '7. d Paris Agreement'. Available at: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=XXVII-7-d&chapter=27&clang=_en#EndDec (Accessed: 16 December 2023).

Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán (2015) 'Yucatán. Identidad y cultura Maya'. Available at: <https://www.mayas.uady.mx/> (Accessed: 21 January 2024).

Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán (2023) 'La Ciudad de Mérida en crecimiento urbano desmesurado'. Available at: <https://uady.mx/noticias/url/la-ciudad-de-merida-en-crecimiento-urbano-desmesurado-uady> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

University of Alberta (2017) *Smart Cities Timeline*. Canada: University of Alberta. Available at: <https://sites.ualberta.ca/~rshields/f/SMARTciestimeline.pdf> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

U.S. Trade and Development Agency (2021) 'Global Partnership for Climate-Smart Infrastructure'. Available at: <https://www.usda.gov/global-partnership-for-climate-smart-infrastructure/> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

U.S. Trade and Development Agency (2022) 'USTDA Advances Southern Mexico's Transportation Goals'. Available at: <https://www.usda.gov/ustda-advances-southern-mexicos-transportation-goals/> (Accessed: 7 January 2024).

Vector (2023) 'Car2x / V2x'. Available at: <https://www.vector.com/int/en/know-how/v2x/> (Accessed: 26 December 2023).

Velco (2023) 'MAAS: REVOLUTION AND STAKES'. Available at: <https://velco.tech/en/maas-revolution-and-stakes/> (Accessed: 26 December 2023).

Vu, K.M. (2020) 'Sources of growth in the world economy: a comparison of G7 and E7 economies', in *Measuring Economic Growth and Productivity*. Elsevier, pp. 55–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817596-5.00004-4>.

Weiss, M.C., Bernardes, R.C. and Consoni, F.L. (2017) 'Cidades inteligentes: casos e perspectivas para as cidades brasileiras.', *Revista Tecnológica da Fatec Americana*, 05(01). Available at: <https://www.fatec.edu.br/revista/index.php/RTecFatecAM/issue/view/10> (Accessed: 24 December 2023).

11 Figures and Tables Sources

Figures

Figure 1: Merida City location. Elaborated by author, 2023.

Figure 2: Research flow diagram. Elaborated by author, 2023.

Figure 3: Sustainable Development Goals. Source: United Nations, 2023. (Accessed: 15 December 2023):

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/news/communications-material/>

Figure 4: Smart City fields of action (Giffinger et al. 2007). Elaborated by author based on Giffinger et al. 2007), 2023.

Figure 5: Smart City Wheel. Elaborated by the author based on Boyd Cohen (2013), 2023. (Accessed: 15 December 2023):

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320860098_Dubai_A_Pioneer_Smart_City_in_the_Arabian_Territory/figures?lo=1

Figure 6: Walkability Evaluation. Arellana et al., 2020, p. 189. (Accessed: 28 December 2023): <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/01441647.2019.1703842?src=getftr>

Figure 7: Mexico Map. Elaborated by the author based on Google | INEGI 2024, 2023. (Accessed: 04 January 2024):

<https://www.google.com/maps/@23.8518013,-103.0993169,5.46z?entry=ttu>

Figure 8: Mexico's Political Division. Elaborated by the author based on INEGI (2024), 2023. (Accessed: 04 January 2024):

<https://cuentame.inegi.org.mx/territorio/extension/default.aspx?tema=T>

Figure 9: Mexico Regions. Elaborated by the author based on the description of INEGI (2018), 2024.

(Accessed: 05 January 2024):

<https://www.inegi.org.mx/rnm/index.php/catalog/223/datafile/F25/V3358>

Figure 10: South-east Region. Source: Elaborated by author based on Google Maps, 2024. (Accessed: 12 January 2024):

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Pen%C3%ADnsula+de+Yucat%C3%A1n/@19.1060269,->

[92.1151945,7.46z/data=!4m6!3m5!1s0x8f59e3c0b627dc33:0x30ae11a8a469643!8m2!3d18.806656!4d-89.3985283!16zL20vMDRsenM4?entry=ttu](https://www.google.com/maps/place/Pen%C3%ADnsula+de+Yucat%C3%A1n/@19.1060269,-92.1151945,7.46z/data=!4m6!3m5!1s0x8f59e3c0b627dc33:0x30ae11a8a469643!8m2!3d18.806656!4d-89.3985283!16zL20vMDRsenM4?entry=ttu)

Figure 11: Merida City location. Elaborated by author, 2023.

Figure 12: Merida Geomorphology. Source: Geoportal de Mérida Yucatán, 2023

(Accessed: 05 January 2024): <https://geoportal.merida.gob.mx/>

Figure 13: Road network and urbanized areas of the municipality of Merida. Source: Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2020, p.14. (Accessed: 12 January 2024):

https://isla.merida.gob.mx/serviciosinternet/ordenamientoterritorial/docs/PIMUS_2040.pdf

Figure 14: Modal split in Merida. Source: Instituto Municipal de Planeación, 2020, p. 13.

(Accessed: 12 January 2024):

https://isla.merida.gob.mx/serviciosinternet/ordenamientoterritorial/docs/PIMUS_2040.pdf

Figure 15: Paseo de Montejo Avenue. Source: Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y

Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 170. (Accessed: 13 January 2024):
<https://mexico.itdp.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/mcx-libro-completo-DIGITAL-Baja.pdf>

Figure 16: Comparison of cross sections of Paseo Montejo. Source: Instituto de Políticas para el Transporte y Desarrollo, México, 2023, p. 174. (Accessed: 13 January 2024):
<https://mexico.itdp.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/mcx-libro-completo-DIGITAL-Baja.pdf>

Figure 17: Bicycle racks in public transport in Merida. Source: Gobierno del Estado de Yucatán, p. 15. (Accessed: 13 January 2024): <https://vayven.yucatan.gob.mx/files/get/148>

Figure 18: En Bici campaign. Source: Ayuntamiento de Mérida, 2023 (Accessed 13 January 2024): <https://www.merida.gob.mx/movilidad/en-bici.php>

Tables

Table 1: Table 1: Main Passenger Modal Options.
Elaborated by author based on Jean-Paul Rodrigue (2020) (Accessed: 25 December 2023):
<https://transportgeography.org/contents/chapter5/transportation-modes-modal-competition-modal-shift/passenger-modal-options/>

Table 2: Summary and comparison among concepts. Elaborated by author, 2023. Based on Chapters 3 & 4.

Table 3: Distribution of points in 2021 by evaluation axis of Mérida, Yucatán.
Source: Pérez Campos, García Romero and Medina Martínez, 2021, p. 53. (Accessed: 13 January 2024):
https://ciclociudades.s3.us-west-2.amazonaws.com/Ranking%20Ciclociudades%202021_highres_16082022.pdf

Table 4: Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Merida. Elaborated by author, 2024.

12 Attachments

Figure 2: Research flow diagram.
Source: Elaborated by author, 2023. P.13

Table 4: Active Mobility and Smart City approaches in Mérida.
Source: Elaborated by autor, 2024. P. 58

Active Mobility				Smart City
Complete Street Project: Paseo de Montejo	Complete Street Project		Monitoring	C5i - Security
Investment allocated from the Federal Expenditure Budget for bicycle mobility	Investment		Bike sharing system	Air Quality Monitoring System
Financing credits to state workers for the purchase of bicycles	Investment		Public Transport	En Bici transport system that provides a bicycle rental service through an app where you can reserve and return a bicycle, look for free parking spots, availability of bikes, and register the end of the trip
Tax benefits to companies, businesses and stores to acquire bikes for their workers	Investment		MaaS & MOD	Integrated Transportation System: Metropolitan System of Friendly and Sustainable Mobility, also known as Va y Ven
Bike credit program "Impulso a la movilidad sostenible" that covers 50% of the purchase of a bike and allows to be paid in installments	Intermodality		Investment	Uber, Didi, En Bici
Bike integration through racks in public transport units, Bikes parking	Intermodality		Investment	USTDA awarded a technical assistance grant to Yucatan State through the Institute of Mobility and Territorial Urban Development to modernize the public transportation system in Mérida.
En Bici transport system that provides a bicycle rental service through an app.	Bike rental service		International cooperation & Education	Latin American branch of the Smart City Expo World Congress: Smart City Expo Latam Congress – SCEL
Creation of citizen council for promotion of bike use	Citizen participation		Infrastructure	Smart traffic lights for pedestrians controlled and monitored through C5i
Cicloranking	Monitoring and Evaluation		Infrastructure	
Bicycle routes	Bike Routes		Infrastructure	

Fátima Xóchitl Bravo Lara
Berlin, Germany, 2024

